

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

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Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	
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List of abbreviation

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and natural heritage

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In the chapters and in the paragraphs in regular style minor changes have been introduced. The paragraph 2.2.3 and the chapter 5 are new.

Summary

This report presents and accompanies the launch of the RURITAGE Atlas, an innovative mapping system for rural territories, developed for the Heritage-led Rural Regeneration Strategies through the work done under Task 1.3. The Atlas represents an integrated digital environment where information about the RURITAGE territories is enabled by a WEB GIS integrated in the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem. The information has been generated by extracting knowledge from RURITAGE Role Models (RMs) and Replicators (Rs).

The report is structured as following:

- The first chapter describes the Atlas conceptual and operational framework, detailing the objectives, methodology, contributions of partners and the relation with other project activities;

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- The second chapter describes the data gathering process, objectives, modalities and criteria and describing the campaigns performed to extract data, information and knowledge from RMs and Rs;
- The third chapter deals with data processing, analysis and interpretation, describing the process of moving from raw data (came from RMs and Rs) to processed and enriched data;
- The fourth chapter describes the process of development and implementation of the Atlas architecture, detailing the Atlas architecture concept, the georeferenced system of mapping, data management and visualization, as well as the development of visual narratives.
- The fifth chapter includes insights about ATLAS user-friendliness after the first period review. It describes the process for improving the tool.

1. The Atlas conceptual and operational framework

1.1 Introduction

The RURITAGE Atlas is the output of the innovative rural landscape creative mapping delivered by Task 1.3 “Innovative Rural Landscape Mapping (RURITAGE Atlas)”. It has been conceived and designed for surveying and making available the multiple and rich functions of rural areas and human-landscape interactions by building an integrated digital environment based on WebGIS where data, maps, images, models and other information generated by extracting knowledge from RURITAGE Role Models (RMs) and Replicators (Rs) are linked and georeferenced. It provides the data visualisation and data management of the RMs and Rs’ cultural and natural heritage (CHN) features, land uses and human interactions with those assets, by building the narratives of CHN in rural areas.

The Atlas provides an interactive and connected environment via Open Street Map, where the information has been collected, spatialized and organized. The mapping concerns RURITAGE RMs and Rs’ territories. The Atlas contents have been created through a collaborative mapping methodology addressed to identify the territories features – cultural natural heritage, both tangible and intangible, and human interactions with RMs and Rs territories – by both extracting local knowledge and performing a desk review.

The data gathered and processed are represented and displayed to be accessed and navigated according to an integral information management concept, able to support the replication and upscaling of the heritage-led strategies.

The information can be visualized and inquired. The availability of different kinds of visualization of the stored information, which is managed through databases, offers the possibility to focus either on the single RM and R, or the SIAs or on crosscutting features.

The Atlas will be accessible through an OPEN ONLINE DATA PLATFORM developed and implemented in the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem (D5.3) where the RURITAGE Practices Repository, the RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learned (D1.1 and D1.2) and the monitoring results (WP4) will be enabled through the Atlas innovative rural landscape creative mapping. The Atlas allows to link the georeferenced identification of the Systemic Innovation Areas and RMs and Rs’ assets. D1.3 and D5.3 are complementary for fully achieving the final Atlas interface, functions and interactions within the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem as a whole, according to RURITAGE overall methodology.

Figure 1 Relation between RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem and Atlas

The RURITAGE Atlas is now online at the URL: www.ruritage-ecosystem.eu/atlas

1.2 Objectives and methodology

RURITAGE **Atlas strategy for conceptualising, collecting and representing** data aimed at achieving an integrated vision of the RMs and Rs' assets, by combining the physical natural features with the human and cultural interactions with those territories over time. Features and change dynamics linkable to the regeneration processes have been especially stressed. Furthermore, a comprehensive descriptive approach has been combined with an analytical vision to create layers of local knowledge for the coherent development of the RURITAGE Atlas as a structural component of the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem.

The RURITAGE **Atlas approach** is based on the cultural landscape concept of human interactions with natural areas, that has created a cultural integration through a number of factors. The Atlas also includes economic and social factors that are able to underline those economic and social potentials that can push resilience and social cohesion in the RURITAGE territories. It addresses specific features, indeed, in the aim of stressing the features of the regeneration processes through the end-user's participation in data providing. Despite the number of historical and cultural layers of landscapes, rather than focusing on the historical dynamics of landscape creation, the mapping underlines the characteristics of the places and their potentials.

The Atlas deals with the establishment and implementation of the RURITAGE Landscapes Mapping Approach in order to defining a system able to describe and characterise landscapes and ecosystems for building RURITAGE knowledge of rural regeneration processes, according to WP1 objectives.

The Atlas is conceived to provide information on the basis of RMs and Rs territories' potential, points of strength and capability to improve by replicating and tailoring the good practices that have been identified. The landscape mapping – and consequently the data gathering – is conceived in a conceptual framework aimed at the identification of: Resources and their Exploitation, Identities and the Sense of place, Temporal and Spatial Dynamics.

For Replicators, some specific negative gaps in landscape perception have been stressed.

TABLE 1. CONCEPTUALISATION AND ATTRIBUTES CLUSTERING

	Characteristics:	SPACE/TIME Dynamics
RURITAGE Territories	Territories' topography	
	Morphological character	
	Physical features	
	Natural Areas	
	Agriculture compared to other land uses	
	Structural Natural Risks	
	Main uses of the areas	
	Typical productions	
	Sites with historic/cultural/natural/social interest	
	CH Declarations	
	Architectural Heritage	
	Reuses and Rehabilitations approach	
	Public functions	
	Extraterritorial connections	
	Accessibility	
	Hubs	
Rural Contexts	Intangible heritage	
	Historicized process	
	Cultural Memories and Identities	
	Traditional and innovative arts/cultural events	
	Itineraries and ways	
	Uses of public open spaces	
	Popular traditions	
	Historical Main Changes	
	Periodical Dynamics	
	Cultural Tourism	
	Structural changes	Post WWII
	Contingent changes	Post trauma
	Temporary uses	Seasonality
	Land uses characterization	Long period
Urban/Rural Interactions	Boundaries areas	Spatial Relations
	Function Relationships	
	Distances	Mobility
	Governance	
	Public Facilities	
Elements of disturbance and interference	High impact infrastructural elements	
	Modification due to implantations of renewable energy plants	
	Perception modification due to instalment of huge elements (advertising, screens)	

	New buildings or group of buildings, settlements and activities that affect the character of the landscape	
	Damages of landscape due to quarries, waste facilities, improper road management	

Basing on this conceptualisation, the Questionnaires for RMs and Rs' data gathering have been built. Layers and attributes for the Atlas mapping have been reviewed and re-clustered following the answers provided and the lack of information (see Table 2).

According with this mapping approach, RURITAGE territories have been mapped, visualized and narrated within the Atlas according to an approach that isn't generalist but finalized to RURITAGE objectives. The result is a combination of both collaborative mapping and of a tailored methodology finalized to the project challenges.

The mapped features don't aim at reaching a complete overview or a properly "cultural landscape" identification, but by critically completing the data gathered through a desk review, the Atlas represents RURITAGE rural territories according to the RMs and Rs' consciousness of their regeneration process, both done or to be enhanced. Its borders and its quantitative as well as qualitative features, thus, address each RMs and Rs' main focus and RURITAGE Systemic Innovation challenges.

The overall **methodology** for defining the RURITAGE Atlas both **interface and attributes** has taken into account a **twofold goal**: on one hand, interface and attributes aim at underlining the rural challenges and the crosscutting issues identified in RURITAGE; on the other hand, RMs and Rs have been recognized as the main actors (both as providers of information and as end-users).

As a result, in order to create the information system knowledge representation of the RURITAGE rural areas:

1. At data gathering stage, both "the common" and/or "the peculiar" features of each SIA and RM/Rs have been mapped and stressed;
2. At data visualization stage, the entry points to the Atlas follow the overall RURITAGE narrative based on SIAs, RMs, Rs, and identified rural challenges.

The mapping process includes a double conceptual and operational path. In Task 1.3 all data have been organised and visualised through QGIS free open source Geographic Information System to identify and spatialise areas, borders, features and layers. An integrated work with Task 5.1 allows the georeferenced information migrating into the RURITAGE Ecosystem platform in order to achieve a new kind of usability of the georeferenced data to be more easily navigated and inquired by users. The aim of this process, in fact, is going beyond a GIS system visualization towards a richer and a strongly user-friendly accessing data usability, coherently with the creative mapping conceived.

The access to the database takes place through dedicated menu and icons. These entries include the access to libraries and archives where the data have been stored.

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A mock-up of this graphical interface has been produced to make accessible the Atlas (M13) with data stored for the following RURITAGE implementation. A further development of the Graphical User Interface has been studied and deployed to provide an easy access to the information in the database also linkable to the navigation in the Atlas (M 28). The final version of the interface and the functions will be delivered within the RURITAGE Ecosystem Platform (D5.3).

The landmarks in mapping provide rich and various narratives of the SIAs, both written and visual, by showing the **peculiarities of each RMs and Rs landscape: topography, sites, built/unbuilt environment, activities and main functions, land uses, infrastructures, rural/peri-urban and urban interactions, itineraries and other features, including Cultural Natural Heritage and (specifically for Rs) elements of disturbance and interference**. The mapping also considered a temporal approach in order to create a dynamic understanding of the areas' development and their seasonal characterisations, when relevant. Analysis, mapping and data management have been addressed to underline all SIAs features and activities in a cross-cutting vision (e.g. CNH analyses, rural productions, buildings for hospitality, activities inherent migrants, religious itineraries, festivals, risks areas, narratives).

Their identification and representation have been conceived as an integrated survey, performed:

- by desk research and review
- by exploiting local knowledge through data gathering from RMs and Rs.

According to this twofold approach a **'creative' mapping methodology** has been developed. It consists in a co-mapping and a collaborative data collecting in order to achieve a rich environment exploiting both the literature together to local knowledge. A traditional documentation survey has been combined with a participative data collection.

The creative mapping methodology is composed of the following steps:

1. Firstly, the desk surveying has produced two articulated questionnaires for gathering data from extracting contributions RMs and Rs as local knowledge generators. By this approach the local representatives have contributed in co-mapping its own area characterisations both indirectly by answering questions and directly by drawing into maps and pictures, as well as sending documentation. RMs and Rs have been asked:
 - i. to answer questions by providing quantitative and qualitative data by filling in the questionnaire by multiple-choice or by a descriptive free text
 - ii. to draw maps and pictures
 - iii. to send documentation
 - iv. to provide links
 - v. special formats for 3D modelling have been also required for some Rs
2. Secondly, data collected into the Atlas have been processed, validated and harmonized by POLITICO team desk review. When data were incomplete, information have been searched to complete data. This integration especially concerns the cultural heritage features of the

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territories and the historical information, that have been accomplished by literature review. The gathered data formats have been checked and transformed into required standard format.

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The above outlined objectives and methodologies are the basis of this report and of the delivered version of the Atlas. They permeate the process of the Atlas building and the integrated work within the RURITAGE project. The following chapters illustrate this process.

1.3 Contributions of partners

POLITO: coordination of the Task, development of the deliverable.

For all the duration of the Task 1.3 (M2-10), the Atlas development has always been extensively discussed and permanently updated with the partner participating to the Task, especially WP1 leader TECNALIA, in order to agree with a shared timetable. The shaping of the Atlas mapping and interface has been checked with the project coordinator UNIBO in order to create the needed coherence, articulation and strategies of the RURITAGE project, and the information to be collected have been coordinated with RMs and Rs.

TECNALIA: coordination of WP1, link with D1.1 (RURITAGE Practices Repository) and D1.2 (RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learned). Development of section 4.4.2.

UNIBO: coordination, link with the whole project. Development of section 4.4.1

RMs and Rs: providers of data, co-developers of the Atlas contents and documentation.

1.4 Relation with other project activities

All the work delivered in Task 1.3 has been conceived as an integrated process with the other project activities, and has been discussed and agreed with RURITAGE coordinator, WP1 leader and other relevant project partners. It took also advantage from remote meetings, such as the monthly Systemic Innovation Board and the Replicator Forum, as well as face to face workshops organised within the RURITAGE project framework. Ad hoc bilateral remote meetings with RMs and Rs representatives responsible of the Atlas development and implementation have been organised.

In particular, during the RURITAGE Training workshop in Valladolid and the development workshop in Heraklion (WP2) face to face meetings with RMs and Rs have been organised in order to better specify requested data and processes. These opportunities raised the awareness on the importance of building the Atlas collectively and in understanding its objectives.

At first, the **Galway Steering Committee** (November 2018) represented a valuable opportunity to get to know a RM area as well as its tangible and intangible cultural heritage features. This meeting helped in defining the conceptual framework for features identification within the mapping system.

Then, in occasion of the **Valladolid Training Workshop** (19th-22nd March 2019), in which RMs and Rs representatives have participated as well as all the KFPs, POLITO has provided an information desk

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where RMs and Rs could ask to explain modalities and criteria for filling the questionnaire. During the **Heraklion Development Workshop** (27th-30th May 2019), other possibilities of Atlas exploitation were discussed with RMs and Rs representative, local stakeholders, representatives of additional RMs and Rs, representatives of the Board of Investors and representatives of all the KFPs. A **workshop session on RURITAGE Atlas** in the context of the “Insights from the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem” was organised. The workshop has been repeated three times for three different small groups of partners, for better interacting with all participants. During this workshop, the ATLAS concept, its development, and its modalities for navigating and inquiry have been shown to the partners.

Task 1.3 has especially complied with the integrated work of the knowledge base building of the overall RURITAGE project of **WP1** (especially with Task 1.1 and 1.2) and **WP5** for the coherent implementation of the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem (link with Task 5.1, but also other WP5 tasks and related key partners). In particular, it complies with the objective of WP1 in providing a comprehensive quantitative and qualitative baseline of the state of the art by linking information gathered from RMs and Rs. As the result of Task 1.1 and 1.2, two repositories have been created: the Practices Repository (D1.1) and the Inventory of Lesson Learned (D1.2). Since the Practices are strictly related to the RMs, they have also been made available in a schematic summary on the Atlas, together with the other information collected (see figure page 5). WP5 will make possible to query RMs’ Best Practices through the Atlas.

2. Data Gathering

2.1 Data gathering process description

The current deliverable and the RURITAGE Atlas are based on the data processing (analysis, interpretation, desk review, and exploitation) of all the gathered data.

Data gathering campaigns have been performed by actively involving RMs and Rs through a collaborative approach. POLITO has delivered questionnaires for RMs and Rs and constantly provided desk support and advices. Other activities, such as bilateral meetings and collateral meetings in conjunction with other project activities also took place to support a comprehensive understanding and improving the data gathering.

Two data gathering main campaigns have been designed:

- The Summer campaign: RMs data gathering
- The Winter campaign: RMs data refining/integration and Rs data gathering
- Additional campaign for Rs: after the recommendation to add demographics and eventually historical information made by the reviewers, bilateral meetings were organized especially with Rs in order to extract additional data and information

2.1.1 Collaborative methodology

A collaborative methodology based on questionnaires was implemented as an innovative rural landscape data gathering for mapping. The data gathering methodology, in fact, aimed at activating a collaborative and creative survey for acquiring information and materials from RMs and Rs. It capitalized the local knowledge in order to identify the most relevant features to be visualized and queried within the Atlas mapping system, according to the specificities of each RM/R rural landscape and related SIAs.

This approach to rural landscape data gathering allowed RMs and Rs to actively participate in a process of definition of the features of their areas, primarily at physical and geographical level by drawing the boundaries of their area of interest, as well as by defining the most relevant elements they recognize as representatives of their rural area, including its tangible and intangible cultural natural heritage together to all potential elements of regeneration, and of the SIA they are associated.

The POLITO desk review checked the usability and the completeness of information, and the format provided. Furthermore since, as will be further detailed later on, in most cases RMs and Rs representatives, gave a huge amount of data potentially associated to the required questions, a choice and a selection of data and materials to shape the information was needed.

2.1.2 Modalities and criteria

Instructions with modalities and criteria for filling the answers in the questionnaire were provided with the questionnaires, including copyright requirements for the attached documentation (see paragraph 3.3). Representatives of each RMs and Rs have been assisted by POLITO team in every

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step of data gathering, via email, bilateral communications and during remote meetings of the SIB and the Replicator Forum.

The Summer campaign questionnaire was associated to the Data Gathering campaign launched

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by the WP1 coordinator and including questionnaires for D1.1. and D1.2. The Winter campaign was launched autonomously following in time the other WP1 tasks questionnaires for D1.1 (Practices Repository), D1.2 (Lessons Learned), D1.4 (Replicators' Baseline).

2.2 From RMs data to Rs Data

2.2.1 Summer campaign: RMs data gathering

The first campaign for the development of the Atlas was launched in July 2018 and the gathering of information lasted until February 2019. The campaign was addressed to the following 12 RMs:

RM1 Camino de Santiago (Spain)

RM2 MARIA-UT (Romania)

RM3 Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)

RM4 Coffee production in World Heritage landscape (Colombia)

RM5 Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy)

RM6 Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece)

RM8 The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)

RM9 Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)

RM10 Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)

RM11 A CNH-led approach in Austratt manorial landscape (Norway)

RM12 Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain)

RM13 Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland)

RM7 UGHP has not been included in the campaign since it withdrew from the project at an early stage for internal issues. UGHP has been later substituted and replaced by TakeArt, that has been involved in the second campaign.

The questionnaire was delivered as a template (Excel format composed of 8 sheets in attach, see Annex I) to be filled by RMs. The first sheet contained the instructions, the second one the questions addressed to all RMs. The following 6 sheets referred to the 6 Systemic Innovation Areas and each RM was asked to fill in and provide information and supporting material regarding its specific SIA. Questions, in fact, have been specified according the SIA challenges in order to create a coherent characterisation of the local territory.

The questionnaire also required to attach a wide range of documentation. The quality and the nature of the documentation - such as maps, pictures, videos, books pages, guides – was also a point in order to properly use it for the Atlas.

The compilers were asked to identify each documentation:

1. By denominating each document attached by referring to the list of questions/answers

2. By describing the document with a strict complete caption.
3. By identifying the formats (e.g. jpg, png, pdf, tiff)
4. By requiring as minimum quality format (600 dpi)
5. By specifying copyrights and other restrictions
6. RMs were also asked to produce a map of their territory

Figure 2 Summer Campaign template

The main aim of the summer campaign has been to obtain from RMs data, information and material suitable for mapping their landscape through the specification of their areas and its features.

Questions have been addressed to defining the perimeter of influence of each RMs, and for specifying its features according to their SIAs. A second layer has been addressed to gather data for mapping long-term and short-term dynamics of change. Long term has been defined as covering till 100 years back. Short term has been defined as post WWII. Besides this common definition, different timing possibilities have been considered for each RM, allowing them to define long and short term changes according to their historical, cultural and contextual specificities.

More in details, the second sheet, containing the **questions to all RMs**, asked them to provide:

- Indication of the borders delimitating the CNL Cultural Natural Landscape area directly

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- or indirectly involved in currently interactions by using simple maps;
- Indication of the borders delimitating the CNL Cultural Natural Landscape directly or indirectly involved in past interactions (providing a significant temporal frame) by using simple maps;
- Digitised version of their most recent cadastre and associated cadastre data;
- Digitised reproduction of their most ancient geometrical cadastre;
- Digitised reproduction of maps providing evidence of relevant changes post WWII or other relevant historical events;
- Information and supporting documentation about most relevant large-scale (national/international) or small-scale (local) event that drove/generated changes in the area;
- Recent and ancient visual documentation of the area and buildings (i.e. photographs, videos, 3D models, architectural drawings, illustrations) including touristic information;
- Any other kind of mapping and digital products (i.e GIS project, 3D models, video, website ...) and resources related to the RM area.

The following sheets contained questions addressed to specific SIA.

Pilgrimage Role Models (RM1 and RM2) have been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant historical and current (if changed) towns of the itinerary;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings of the itinerary, distinguishing religious sites and pilgrims' services and providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings that have recently been included in the itinerary (indicating a significant temporal frame);
- Provide information and access to inventories covering the national heritage sites/buildings in the area;
- Provide information and digitised reproduction of relevant historical guides of the itinerary;

Sustainable food production Role Models (RM3 and RM4) have been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings linkable to food production in the area, specifying their functions and providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- Provide information and access to inventories covering the national heritage

sites/buildings in the area;

- List and associate to the recent cadastre area land uses (type of rural productions).

Migration Role Models (RM5 and RM6) have been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings linkable to migrant hospitality in the area, providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant rehabilitated historic buildings, providing information about previous uses, ownership and rehabilitation temporal frame and providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- Provide information and access to inventories covering the national heritage sites/buildings in the area.

Art&festival Role Model (RM8) has been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites (open air) and buildings linkable to cultural activity in the area, providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites and buildings linkable to other art&festival uses ((i.e. residences for artists, tourism operators, and soon...), providing visual and other supporting documentation.

Resilience Roles Models (RM9 and RM10) have been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings linkable to cultural activities in the area, providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings used for resilience training activities, providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map sites of traditional storytelling related to natural environment, providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the main risks areas;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant sites/buildings linkable to risks mitigation actions.

Landscape Role Models (RM11, RM12 and RM13) have been asked to:

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant physical elements of the Cultural Natural Heritage (heritage buildings/sites, other buildings of local history, art and cultural buildings and sites, vineyards, rural food production, crafts productions and other relevant land uses), providing visual and other supporting documentation;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant in terms of heritage towns within the Cultural Natural Heritage site;
- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant historical infrastructures

crucial in linking the elements;

- List, describe and indicate in a simple map the most relevant recent infrastructures crucial in linking the elements.

2.2.2 Winter campaign: RMs and Rs data gathering

The second campaign for the development of the Atlas was launched in February 2019 and the gathering of information lasted until May 2019.

The winter campaign was addressed to the following 13 RMs and 6 Rs:

RM1 Camino de Santiago (Spain)

RM2 MARIA-UT (Romania)

RM3 Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)

RM4 Coffee production in World Heritage landscape (Colombia)

RM5 Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti province (Italy)

RM6 Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos island (Greece)

RM7 Take Art: sustainable rural arts development (UK)

RM8 The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)

RM9 Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)

RM10 Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)

RM11 A CNH-led approach in Austratt manorial landscape (Norway)

RM12 Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain)

RM13 Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland)

R1 Old traditions&modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg (Austria)

R2 A brand for discovering local food products and traditions in Rogaland (Norway)

R3 Working for CNH as a way for migrants' integration in Geo-N (Germany)

R4 Festival of love – arts connecting heritage and tradition (Slovenia)

R5 Social innovation&local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche Region (Italy)

R6 Integrated management of Madra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins (Turkey)

The new RM7 TakeArt (UK) has been involved in the second campaign, replacing (amendment completed at M10)UGHP.

Starting from the performed analysis on data and information provided by RMs during the first campaign, the second campaign was conceived to extend the questions for each SIA to all other RMs in order to create a common general framework of description for mapping landscapes. SIA-related answers received from RMs were used to reformulate questions for all RMs of other SIAs in order to map cross-cutting aspects useful for Rs.

The aim has been to obtain data for mapping all various features and human interactions with

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the territories in order to create more articulated information for the end-users. The possibility to navigate and enquiry this rich framework will enable Rs to search for cross-cutting information.

The second campaign also allowed to: (i) refine the questionnaires, (ii) ask for integrations and for the completion of the information provided by RMs, (iii) launch the data gathering for Rs, in order to understand and geo-reference the most relevant interactions between people and their territories in the RMs and Rs areas. The same campaign was indeed circulated among Rs, including additional questions specifically addressed to them.

Considering the obstacles encountered during the first campaign by RMs in using the previous Template in Excel format file provided (see paragraph 2.3) and in providing on time the information, a new kind of template has been adopted in order to make easier and more effective both the fulfilment of the campaign as well as the data processing. In this second questionnaire, there was a big effort in making the requests easier by giving up some strict requirements in documentation both formats and identification and definition.

This questionnaire consisted of an A4 questionnaire (word file) with a list of questions, linked to two different templates for answering:

- i. a “question template” to fill in by multiple-choice and/or or by a descriptive free text;
- ii. an interactive “map template” to point in the Google my map.

The “question template” (questions 1, 5, 2, 8) aimed at acquiring general information and descriptions of the material provided. The “map template” requiring georeferenced information asked RMs to answer through the (kmz file) (questions 1,3,4,5,6,7,9).

Overall, RMs and Rs have been asked to upload scans (or other useful reproduction or accessible links) of relevant historical and recent visual (e.g. photographs, engravings, videos, architectural drawings, maps, etc.), audio (e.g. videos, interviews,), and textual material (e.g. documents, travel literature, and other relevant literary descriptions, etc.), or information about objects (e.g. coins, archaeological remains, etc.).

The complete questionnaires circulated among RMs and Rs are reported in Annex I. According to the open access policy adopted by RURITAGE, all the collected raw data will also be uploaded in Zenodo repository, after proper assessment together with data owner and copyright rules.

Here below a synthetic description of the questionnaires circulated among RMs and Rs:

Question 1: SIA Area

The first question aimed at co-mapping RMs and Rs characterisations.

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It asked to RMs and Rs to:

- (Q1a) Draw on simple map the perimeters of the SIA, intended as area of action of each RM/R according to RURITAGE objectives. The question has been declined according to the specificities of each SIA.
- (Q1b) Select the level of interaction of each CNL with other SIA (apart from the one each RM/R belongs to).
- (Q1c) Draw in a simple map other areas of influence related to their SIA. Again, the questions have been differentiated according to SIA.
- (Q1d) Indicate in the map and provide information about relevant changes in past/recent times;
- (Q1e) Select and map eventual characterizations related to their area, such as natural area, rural area, unpopulated area, historic urban center, area of gentrification, area of old/recent industrialization, area under the risk of natural disaster, etc.
- (Q1f) Provide access – if any – to inventories of heritage/sites buildings in their area.

Question 2: Land uses

The second question was addressed to acquire information about land uses in RMs' and Rs' areas. To do so, RMs and Rs have been asked to:

- Indicate, describe and provide access and/or digitised reproduction (and associated cadastral data) to the most recent cadastre (Q2a)
- Indicate, describe and provide access and/or digitised reproduction (and associated cadastral data) to other ancient geometrical parcel cadastres (Q2b)
- Indicate, describe and provide access and/or digitised reproduction of maps of the area after WWII (or other relevant historical event/trauma) indicating eventual damages and state of the site (Q2c)
- Provide digitised reproductions of historical maps of the area (Q2d)
- Indicate and describe the recent situation regarding prevalent land uses in the area, by providing thematic maps – if available – with uses description (Q2e)
- Indicate and describe any craft productions, especially those related to local traditions (Q2f).

Question 3: Sites

Question 3 aimed at acquiring info about the most relevant sites of the RM/R area. It asked to RMs and Rs to:

- (Q3a) Provide information and indicate in the map any UNESCO World Heritage Site within the area
- (Q3b) Provide information and indicate in the map any other listed (national, local) sites
- In both cases, the questionnaire asked to indicate the inscription year and draw in the

map the boundaries of the site (or indicate the individual buildings).

- (Q3c) Provide information and indicate in the map any other historic site that could be relevant for local history and traditions
- (Q3d) Provide information and indicate in the map any historical/traditional itinerary
- (Q3f) Provide information and indicate in the map any site that has become specifically popular

Question 4: Open Air activities

Question 4 aimed at acquiring info about the most relevant open-air activities in the RM/R area. It asked to RMs and Rs to:

- (Q4a) List and describe most relevant periodic festivals, detailing the type of festival (art, food, religious, other). It also asked to draw the related boundaries in the map and point individual buildings related to festivals;
- (Q4b) List and describe, if any, recurrent/seasonal open-air specific cultural or traditional activities, detailing the type (theatre, exhibition, crafts fair, parade, other). It also asked to draw the related boundaries in the map and indicated the date/period of festival occurrence;
- (Q4c) List and describe any other relevant open-air activity such as daily or periodic food/traditional/antiquities/craft markets;
- (Q4d) List and describe any extraordinary event that was/has been planned in the area, drawing/pointing the related interest area.

Question 5: Historic buildings and monuments

Question 5 aimed at acquiring info about the most relevant historic buildings and monuments in the RM/R area. It asked to RMs and Rs to:

- (Q5a) List, describe and point in the map any UNESCO building in the RM or R area;
- (Q5b) List, describe and point in the map any other listed national/local building in the RM or R area;
- (Q5c) List, describe and point in the map any other building relevant for local history/tradition;
- (Q5d) List, describe and point in the map any relevant historic building that have been devoted to new relevant public/collective activity such as cultural activities, migrants' hospitality, public authorities headquarters, tourism activities;
- (Q5e) List, describe and point in the map any relevant old/historic farm;
- (Q5f) List, describe and point in the map any other relevant recent building that have been built for cultural activities, production, energy production, trade hub, other;
- (Q5g) List, describe and point in the map any other relevant building/site in the RM area;
- (Q5h) Provide additional material/info – if available - related to the CH buildings listed

and pointed, such as: architectural drawing, 3d model, photographs, video.

Question 6: The relation of the RM/R area to the closest urban area

The main aim of question 6 is to explore and analyse the relation among RM/R rural areas and the closest urban environment. It asked to RM/R to:

- (Q6a) Indicate and point/draw in the map the closest and most related urban area, describing the level of relation/dependency;
- (Q6b) Indicate and point/draw in the map cultural organizations and buildings within the RM/R area and/or the closest urban area where they available, such as preservation CH institutions, museums, Eco museums, theatres, libraries, art galleries, public archives, cinemas, archaeological sites;
- (Q6c) Indicate and point/draw in the map important education buildings within the RM/R area and/or the closest urban area where they available, such as primary schools, high schools, universities, others;
- (Q6d) Indicate and point/draw in the map important relevant buildings of local authority and public services within the RM/R area and/or the closest urban area where they available, such as local authority, regional authority, hospitals, health clinics, general markets, specialized markets;
- (Q6e) Indicate and point/draw in the map the access of the RM/R area and the relation between the area and the closest urban area through the most relevant infrastructures, such a highways, national/regional/local streets, bridges, airports, railways, stations;
- (Q6f) Indicate and point/draw in the map further planned/ongoing infrastructures that could be important in linking the area with the region and/or beyond, such as airports, railways, streets, bridges, travel hubs;
- (Q6g) Indicate and point/draw in the map historical infrastructures that have been crucial in linking the area with the region and/or beyond;
- (Q6h) Indicate any extraordinary event planned in the closest urban area and if possible point the interest area in the map.

Question 7: Tourism.

Question 7 aimed at acquiring georeferenced information regarding touristic activities in the RM/R area. It asked to:

- (Q7a) Indicate and point/draw in the map the most important tourist info offices;
- (Q7b) Indicate and point in the map – whenever possible - the most important description panels for sites/buildings of cultural interest, among the ones listed by the RM/R;
- (Q7c) Indicate any other tourist communication campaign by pointing it in the map in

case of interesting specific sites/buildings.

8: Multimedia and Digital Tools.

Question 8 aimed at acquiring, whenever available and/or relevant, multimedia and digital tools related to RMs and Rs area. It asked to RMs and Rs to:

- (Q8a) List, describe and provide access to any kind of mapping and digital products/resources/tools related to the RM/R area, such as GIS, 3D model, Mobile apps, video;
- (Q8b) List, describe and provide access to any kind of movie or advertising that have used the RM/R area as scenario;
- (Q8c) List, describe and provide access to any kind of audio material produced linkable to the RM/R area.

All the questions (from 1 to 8), beside asking georeferenced information by drawing/pointing in the map, asked to upload relevant historical and recent visual and other supporting material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3d models, etc.). Question 8 asked to point/draw in the map the elements only if coherent with the information provided. If not possible, it asked to just fill the answers (without point) and attach visual and supporting material.

The Rs winter campaign included also an additional question addressed specifically to Rs.

Question 9 (Rs): Elements of disturbance

Question 9 aimed at identifying, within Replicators area, the element of disturbance of the cultural natural landscape. It asked to Rs to list, describe and point/draw eventual elements of disturbance that constitute fragmentation or damage of the landscape's perception, such as:

- telecommunications infrastructural elements (base stations for radios, TVs, mobile phones);
- huge transportation infrastructures (highways, canals, tunnels);
- technological infrastructures (gas pipeline, power plant, etc);
- electrical infrastructures (cables, poles);
- renewable energy sources implantations (solar panels, photovoltaics, wind farms);
- instalment of elements, potentially movable, that change the perception of the landscape (large advertisement panels, large LCD screens);
- commercial or industrial or agricultural settlements with their services;
- quarries (active, underused, dismissed);
- waste facilities (active, underused, dismissed); - attraction areas (parks, camping, picnic);
- buildings or groups of buildings that affect the characterization of the landscape (e.g.

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sprawl);

- new buildings that contrast with the cultural natural landscape because of typology, colour, material, decontextualization, etc.
- improper street pavement (asphalt in natural area, improper finishing)
- recurrent collective events that contrast with the existing landscape

Question 10 (Rs): Additional information for 3D modelling and BIM

- Architectural drawings
- dimensional information
- state of site, damages, restoration, historical developments
- additional detailed pictures and historical iconography
- archive textual documentation

Specific requirements input data and documentation have been requested to Rs for generating 3D models to be added to the Atlas through the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem. In this case geometric representations and geographical delimitation and specific formats have been expressly asked.

2.2.3 Additional requests for information and data after first period review report

To meet the requests made by the reviewers, additional data and information have been extracted both through desk research and ad hoc campaigns of data gathering from RMs and Rs.

It should be noted that the new information goes beyond the request. Reviewers asked demographic data and suggested to provide some historical information. By benefitting of the extension of time, the developers some more

In particular:

- Survey about World Heritage Intangible Heritage in the RMs and Rs territories
- RMs and Rs have been asked to provide more specific information about intangible heritage by indicating among the intangible heritage listed by UNESCO those relevant for the area and also indicating additional heritage not listed.
- RMs and Rs have been asked to provide demographic and other quantitative data such as: extension of the area, overall population, density, distribution of population by age, presence of foreign people and migrants (Rs have been also asked to provide economic indicators such as unemployment rate). Initially, those information have been extracted from campaigns already implemented by TEC and CARTIF for the development of the Practices Repository (D1.1) and Replicators Baseline (D1.4). In a second stage, RMs and Rs have been asked to check quantitative data already provided and provide the missing ones. Finally desk research has also checked specific sources.
- Rs have been asked to provide more data, information, maps, cartography and audio-visual material for the development of the Replicators Historical Cultural Natural Heritage Narratives according the topic identified (please see Chapter 5)

TABLE 2. Table of RM Demographics

RM	RM name and country	RM area and administrative borders	Extension of the area	Overall Population	Population Density	Percent distribution of population by age - ageing of population	Migrants presence	Data sources	Validated by RM
RM1	Camino de Santiago-Way of Saint James (Spain)	Provinces of Palencia, Burgos, Leon	The French Way: 400 km across Castile and Leon; 1000 Km across the north of Spain	981.726 inhabitants PROVINCE of Palencia: inhabitants 160.980 (2019); PROVINCE of Burgos 357.070 (2018), PROVINCE of León, 463.746 (2018)	25,07 inhab/ km ² PROVINCES of Palencia: 20 inhab./km ² ; Burgos 25,46 hab./km ² ; León 29,76 inhab/km ²	25,36% over 64 years old (Castile & Leon, 2019).	42% international 58% from other Spanish regions (Castilla y León)	1.D1.1 PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2. Junta de Castilla y Leon: https://conocecastillayleon.jcyl.es/web/es/geografia-poblacion/poblacion.html#:~:text=Seg%C3%BAntos%20datos%20estad%C3%A2sticos,personas%20en%20Castilla%20y%20Le%C3%B3n. 3.Datos macro: https://datosmacro.expansion.com/demografia/estructura-poblacion/espana-comunidades-autonomas/castilla-leon#:~:text=Castilla%20y%20Le%C3%B3n%20cuenta%20con,poblaci%C3%B3n%20de%20las%20comunidades%20aut%C3%B3nomas.&text=Con%20un%2025%2C36%25%2C65%20a%C3%B1os%20entre%20su%20poblaci%C3%B3n	Yes
RM2	Via Mariae / Mária Út / Mary's way (Romania)	Harghita County	6.639 km ²	325.611 inhabitants (Harghita County)	49,05 inhab./km ²	21.,26% over 60 years old forecast for 2050 increase to 32,2%. (2015)	No migrant's presence in Harghita county.	1.D1.1 PRACTICES REPOSITORY	Yes
RM3	Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)	Puglia/Apulia Region	19.540,49 km ²	4.008.296 inhabitants (Apulia Region) Men: 1.950.256 Women: 2.058.040 (2020)	205,33 inhab./km ²	23,2% over 65 years' old, Average age 45 years old (2020)	140.564 Men: 70.784 Women: 69.780 (2020)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2.ISTAT 2020: http://dati.istat.it/	Yes
RM4	Coffee production in World Heritage landscape (Colombia)	Municipalities of Palestina and Salento, Colombia	119 km ² (Palestina) 328 Km ² (Salento) (2020)	Palestina: 15.68 inhabitants Salento: 9529 inhabitants (2020)	Palestina: 131.77 inhab./km ² Salento: 29.05 inhab/km ² (2020)	Older accounts for less than 10%. (2018)	No official information is available (no censuses)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2. https://terridata.dnp.gov.co/index-app.html#/perfiles/17524 3. https://terridata.dnp.gov.co/index-app.html#/perfiles/63690 4. https://terridata.dnp.gov.co/index-app.html#/perfiles/17524 5. https://terridata.dnp.gov.co/index-app.html#/perfiles/63690	Yes
RM5	Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy)	Asti Province, Italy	1600, 00 km ²	213.216 inhabitants Men: 104.470 Women: 108.746 (2020)	141,93 inhab/km ²	12,9% under 14 years old, 24,9% over 64 years old Average age 47 years old (2020)	12,8% (9.699 residents in 2019)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2.ISTAT 2019 3.ISTAT 2020	Yes

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RM6	Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece)	Lesvos Island, Greece	1,632.8 km ²	86,436 inhabitants (2011)	53 inhab/ km ²	No available data	Lesvos received almost half of new arrivals in Greece: 4,108 migrants (49%) (2020)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2.EUROSTAT 2018 3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lesvos 4. https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/1515741/GreeceInFigures_2020Q1_EN.pdf/4ab68b3f-bd6c-d77d-8bf9-cfcbf91aa937 5. https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/79167	Yes
RM7	Take Art: Sustainable Rural Arts Development (UK)	Somerset County, South West, UK	3,452 km ²	559,399 inhabitants 48% of the population live in a Rural area (England: 18%)	162 inhab/km ²	23.2%: over 65 years old (17.7% nationally) (2014)	6% (31,761) born outside the UK 13,600 migrant workers (National Insurance between 2014 and 2017)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2. http://www.somersetintelligence.org.uk/somerset-facts-and-figures/ 3.Census 2011 4.Somerset Intelligence: http://www.somersetintelligence.org.uk/somerset-facts-and-figures/ 5.Stat-Xplore 6.National Insurance	Yes
RM8	The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)	Visegrad town, Hungary	33,3 km ²	10,668 inhabitants (2013) Men 47.9% Women: 52.1%	56.48 inhab. /km ² (2019)	18%: 0-18 years: 58%: 19-64: 24%*: over 64 years Average age 44.6 years old (2013)	Total Foreigners: 0.51% Males 0.24% Women 0.26% (2013)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2. https://www.citypopulation.de/en/hungary/pest/ 3. https://ugeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/en/ba/demografia/dati-sintesi/visegrad/25511363/4	Yes
RM9	Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)	Crete Island, Greece	8,340 Km ² (2016)	631,812 Inhabitants Men: 308,725 Women 323,087(2016)	75.9 inhab/km ²	24% over 65 years old (22% nationally)	No data available	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2.Census 2011 3.Hellenic Statistic Service 2019: https://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/1515741/GreeceInFigures_2020Q1_EN.pdf/4ab68b3f-bd6c-d77d-8bf9-cfcbf91aa937 https://knoema.com/atlas/Greece/Kriti/Total-population	Yes
RM10	Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)	Three Municipalities that make up the borders of the Geopark: Rangarþing; Eystra, Mýrdalshreppur; Skaftárhreppur Municipalities.	9542 km ²	3307 inhabitants. (2020)	0,35 inhab/km ²	17% 65 years or older, (14% nationally)	16.4% (2016) and 22.4% (2018)	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2.Icelandic Association of Local Authorities: https://www.samband.is/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/svaedisaaetlun_hula2008_2020.pdf https://www.samband.is/sveitarfelogin/sudurland/ 3.Statistics Iceland: https://px.hagstofa.is/pxe/pxweb/en/?rxid=7ffad7b0-2f3e-4660-85f9-57b1675b6367 https://px.hagstofa.is/pxi/pxweb/is/lbuar/lbuar_mannfoldi_3_bakgrunnur_Uppruni/MAN43005_px	Yes

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RM1 1	A CNH-led approach in Austrått manorial landscape (Norway)	Ørland municipality	457,07 km ² 429 km ² land area; 28.07 km ² freshwater area)	10,337 inhabitants. (2020) Men: 5,239 Women: 5,084 (2020)	24 inhab/km ² (2020)	20.7% 65 years or older (17.5% nationally)	10.162 immigrants it is expected 2000 more people will move to Ørland in the next few years	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY 2. statistics Norway: www.ssb.no 3. https://www.ssb.no/en/statbank/table/09280/tableViewLayout1/ https://www.ssb.no/kommuneareal/orland 4. https://www.ssb.no/statbank/table/07459/tableViewLayout1/	Yes
RM1 2	Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain)	The area covers two countries (Spain and Portugal) and 633 municipalities. 595 are part of the Spanish region of Castilla y León (NUTS2ES41), the other 38 are located in the Northern region of Portugal (NUTS2PT11).	total area 34,084.22 km ² , 25,347.24 km ² Spanish, 8,736.97 km ² Portuguese	2,660,385 inhabitants; 1,846,517 in Portugal, 813,868 in Spain.	78.5 inhab/km ² , Spain 32.11 inhab/km ² , Portugal 211.35 inhab/km ²	0-14: 13.83%; 15-65: 66.4%; >65: 19.77%. >75: 9.73%	The volume of migrant's resident in the Douro is very low: 43,918 inhabitants representing 1.65% of the total population.	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2. Replicator's elaboration based on official data INE (Spain) and INÉ (Portugal): INÉ (Spain): https://www.ine.es/en/index.htm INÉ (Portugal) https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xppgid=ine_main&xpid=INE	Yes
RM1 3	The Northern Headlands area of Ireland's Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland)	Nine coastal counties of the West of Ireland – Donegal, Leitrim, Sligo, Mayo, Galway, Clare, Limerick, Kerry and Cork, Ireland	2,500km from the village of Muff on the Inishowen Peninsula in County Donegal to Kinsale in West Cork. 4,861 km ² Donegal,	159,192 inhabitants. (2016) in Donegal	32.76 inhab/km ² in Donegal	Average age: 38.5 years in Donegal 37.4 years nationally.	No data available	1.D1.1, PRACTICES REPOSITORY TEC 2. https://failteireland.ie/Failteireland/media/WebsiteStructure/Documents/Wild%20Atlantic%20Way/WAW-NorthernHeadlands-SurfCoast-NoMap-Low-Res.pdf	Yes

Table 3: Replicator demographic

R	R name	R area and admin borders	Extension of Repliator area	Overall Population	Population Density	Percent distribution of population by age - ageing of population	Migrants presence	Economic indicators Unemployment rate % and/or GDP	Data sources	Validated by Repliators
R1	Old traditions and modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg -ARGE - AUSTRIA	A total of 14 municipalities from Austria (9) and Slovenia (5) form the area of the Geopark Karavanke: (Zell/Sele, Gallizien, Eisenkappel/Telezna Kapla, Sittersdorf, Globasnitz/Globasnica, Feistritz ob Bleiburg/Bistrice nad Pliberkom, Bleiburg/Pliberk, Neuhaus, Lavamünd, Črna na Koroškem, Mežica, Prevalje, Ravne na Koroškem and Dravograd). For the development	1067 Km ²	53,000 inhabitants	61.1 inhab/km ²	In the whole of the Geopark area, a considerable ageing of the population has been noted that is comparable to the Slovenian average but is still substantially below the Austrian average.	According to STAT, the Municipality of Globasnitz had 1.598 inhabitants. 1.506 of those were/are Austrian people and 92 are foreign people - by nationality (i. e. 5,8% of foreign people). No specific information on migrants presence available.	The unemployment rate in Geopark regions is 12.18%, much higher than the European average (EU27 – 9.6%), almost twice as high as the Austrian average (6.9%) and somewhat higher than the Slovenian average (11.6%).	1. D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF 2. www.statistik.at 3. http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/environment/earth-sciences/unesco-global-geoparks/list-of-unesco-global-geoparks/austriaslovenia/karawankenkaravanke/	Yes

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		of the baseline, only 1 municipality (Globasnitz/Globasnica) has been considered, because is where the main Pilgrimage place is located.								
R2	Magma UNESCO Global Geopark - NORWAY	Municipalities affected by the actions: Egersund, Lund, Flekkefjord, Sokndal, Bjerkreim	2,329 km2	32,000 inhabitants	13.5 inhab /km2	Most concerns about the aging wave are related to the fact that there are fewer and fewer people in employment per pensioner. This ratio is called the dependence fraction. Employed persons are defined here as all persons of working age (20-64years) and pensioners as all persons who are 65 years or older. Magma Geopark: 2020: 0.34 2030: 0.46 2040: 0.58 2050: 0.64	There are an increasing number of immigrants in the area, but not to the extent that it represents a challenge. International Rate of foreign people 11.7 %	Unemployment rate: 4.25% (01/06/2020)	1. D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF	Yes
R3	Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße Odenwald e.V. - GEON - GERMANY	Countries affected by the actions: Kreis Bergstraße; Kreis Darmstadt-Dieburg; Darmstadt; Freudenberg; Groß-Gerau; Grobostheim; Heidelberg; Kreis Miltenberg; Neckar-Odenwald; Odenwaldkreis; Rhein-Neckar-Kreis	3.500 km2	8,87,850 inhabitants	Around 130 inhab /km2	Population composition: 15% under 15, 66% 16-65; 19% over 65. ageing of population: Average 43.2 years	almost 28% of population had a migration background.	Unemployment rate: 2.3%	1. D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF 2. Baden-Württemberg, 2008. 3. Baden-Württemberg, 2013. 4. https://www.hessen-tourismus.de/en/experience-nature/the-great-outdoors/bergstrasse-odenwald-unesco-global-geopark/	Yes

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R4	Kulturno Izobrazevalno Drustvo KIBLA KULT PROTUR-SLOVENIA	Municipality of Gornja Radgona in Slovenia	74.41 km ²	8,403 inhabitants Men: 49.6% Women: 50.4% (2018) 8417 inhabitants Men: 4,218 Women: 4199 (2020)	112.9 inhab/km ² (National average: 102/km ²)	0-14 years: 1,107 15-64 years: 5,459 65+ years: 1,851 Average age: 44.15 years (2018)	Rate of foreign people: 1.37 % of population Men: 0.79% Women: 0.58% (2018)	GDP per person: 12,437 Unemployment rate 16% (National average 12.3%)	1.D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF 2.Statistical office, Republic of Slovenia: https://pxweb.stat.si/SiStatDb/pxweb/en/10_Dem_soc/10_Dem_soc_05_prebivalstvo_10_stevilo_preb_20_05C40_prebivalstvo_obcine/05C4002S.px/table/tableViewLayout2/ 3. https://www.citypopulation.de/en/slovenia/admin/pomurska/029_gornja_radgona/ 4.AdminStat SLOVENIA: https://ugeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/en/si/demografija/stranieri/gornja-radgona/20635727/4	Yes
R5	Comune di Appignano del Tronto (CoApp) ITALY	Comune di Appignano del Tronto	23.19 km ²	1728 inhabitants Men: 48.8% Women: 51.2% (2018)	74.5 inhab/km ² (2018)	Population growth rate: -2.21% (2018) Average age: 47.9 years old (2018)	Rate of foreign people: 3.59% Men: 1.45% Women: 2.14% (2018)	GDP per person: 22,300 € Unemployment rate: 12%	1.D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF ISTAT 2020 2.AdminStat ITALY: https://ugeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/en/it/demografia/eta/appignano/43003/4	Yes
R6	Integrated Management of Izmir Geopark in Bakircay Basins TURKEY	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality, Districts of Bergama, Dikili and Kinik	2740 km ² (Bergama: 1720 km ² , Kinik: 479 km ² , Dikili: 541km ²)	Bergama: 103 185 inhabitants Dikili: 44 172 inhabitants Kinik: 29 803 inhabitants Project Area: 177160 Inhabitants (2018)	58 inhab/km ²	Population growth rate: 1.33 % (Izmir) 0.85% (Bergama) 1.2% (Dikili) 0.2% (Kinik) (2017)	Immigrants to Izmir 102 776 (2017)	GDP per person: ~ 12344 USD (Izmir) Unemployment rate: 13.8 % (Izmir)	1.D1.4 REPLICATOR BASELINE, CARTIF 2. http://www.izmir.gov.tr/istatistiklerle-izmir 3.AdminStat TURKEY: https://ugeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/en/tr/demografija/popolazione/bergama/22747494/4	Yes

Table 4: Role Models Intangible Heritage

RM No.	Year	UNESCO Intangible heritage	Link	Comments
RM1	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	Confirmed by replicators.
RM2	2017	Cultural practices associated to the 1st of March	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/cultural-practices-associated-to-the-1st-of-march-01287	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage

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	2016	Traditional wall-carpet craftsmanship in Romania and the Republic of Moldova	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/traditional-wall-carpet-craftsmanship-in-romania-and-the-republic-of-moldova-01167	
	2015	Lad's dances in Romania	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/lads-dances-in-romania-01092	
	2013	Men's group Colindat, Christmas-time ritual	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mens-group-colindat-christmas-time-ritual-00865	
	2009	Doina	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/doina-00192	
RM3	2019	Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	Confirmed by replicators.
	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
RM4	2019	Safeguarding strategy of traditional crafts for peace building	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/safeguarding-strategy-of-traditional-crafts-for-peace-building-01480	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
	2017	Colombian-Venezuelan llano work songs	https://ich.unesco.org/en/USL/colombian-venezuelan-llano-work-songs-01285	
RM5	2019	Alpinism	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/alpinism-01471	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
		Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	
		Art of dry stone walling, knowledge and techniques	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393	
		Falconry, a living human heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/falconry-a-living-human-heritage-01209	
		Traditional agricultural practice of cultivating the 'vite ad alberello' (head-trained bush vines) of the community of Pantelleria	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/traditional-agricultural-practice-of-cultivating-the-vite-ad-alberello-head-trained-bush-vines-of-the-community-of-pantelleria-00720	
		Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
RM6	2019	Byzantine chant	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/byzantine-chant-01508	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
		Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	
	2018	Art of dry stone walling, knowledge and techniques	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393	
	2017	Rebetiko	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/rebetiko-01291	
	2014	Know-how of cultivating mastic on the island of Chios	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/know-how-of-cultivating-mastic-on-the-island-of-chios-00993	
	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
RM7				No data available
RM8	2018	Blaudruck/Modrotisk/Kékfestés/Modrotlač, resist block printing and indigo dyeing in Europe	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/blaudruck-modrotisk-kekfestes-modrotlac-resist-block-printing-and-indigo-dyeing-in-europe-01365	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
	2016	Falconry, a living human heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/falconry-a-living-human-heritage-01209	
		Safeguarding of the folk music heritage by the Kodály concept	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/safeguarding-of-the-folk-music-heritage-by-the-kodaly-concept-01177	
	2011	Táncház method: a Hungarian model for the transmission of intangible cultural heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/tanchaz-method-a-hungarian-model-for-the-transmission-of-intangible-cultural-heritage-00515	
RM9	2019	Byzantine chant	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/byzantine-chant-01508	Confirmed by replicators.
		Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	
	2018	Art of dry stone walling, knowledge and techniques	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393	
	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
		There is an effort in process to inscribe the total shepherds' life of Priorities as a particular intangible heritage. It also includes the mitato technique, the specific organization of life in mitato, the oracle tradition through sheep bones, the vow and internal arrangements of conflicts, the specific production of dairy, wool and many other products.	https://l.facebook.com/l.php?u=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.youtube.com%2Fwatch%3Fv%3DkZa4hj54FUg%26fbclid%3DIwAR2jI0o5C073tIC3Eg8kWOYqJ0PCux0LJwSh6wuYER3LxsiLsqGGNlvDyQ8&h=AT35ty2CWitEb_6iGkBGRJ9nFBd3a59eDnKXjNI1N9_VMVtyP0rc5p8GIQrtt1LK9rAkEGvkv3QlhOal6AAwZ9giTgivFyRpPZRuzuh5bYsl5SpB6PZTW9KKoaNalnUqQ	

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RM10				No data available
RM11	2016	Oselvar boat - reframing a traditional learning process of building and use to a modern context	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/oselvar-boat-reframing-a-traditional-learning-process-of-building-and-use-to-a-modern-context-01156	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
RM12	2018	Art of dry stone walling, knowledge and techniques	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
		Tamboradas drum-playing rituals	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/tamboradas-drum-playing-rituals-01208	
	2016	Falconry, a living human heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/falconry-a-living-human-heritage-01209	
	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
RM13	2019	Irish harping	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/irish-harping-01461	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
	2018	Hurling	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/hurling-01263	
	2017	Uilleann piping	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/uilleann-piping-01264	

Table 5: Replicators Intangible Heritage

R No.	Year	UNESCO Intangible heritage	Link	Comments
R1	2019	Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	UNESCO listed intangible heritage not relevant to their specific area and activity
	2018	Avalanche risk management	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/avalanche-risk-management-01380	
	2016	Falconry, a living human heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/falconry-a-living-human-heritage-01209	
		Regional Centers for Craftsmanship: a strategy for safeguarding the cultural heritage of traditional handicraft	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/regional-centres-for-craftsmanship-a-strategy-for-safeguarding-the-cultural-heritage-of-traditional-handicraft-01169	
R2	2016	Oselvar boat - reframing a traditional learning process of building and use to a modern context	https://ich.unesco.org/en/BSP/oselvar-boat-reframing-a-traditional-learning-process-of-building-and-use-to-a-modern-context-01156	UNESCO listed intangible heritage not relevant to their specific area and activity
R3		Lorsch Pharmacopoeia	http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/memory-of-the-world/register/full-list-of-registered-heritage/registered-heritage-page-5/lorsch-pharmacopoeia-the-bamberg-state-library-mscmed1/	Confirmed by Replicators
		Song of the Nibelungs	http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/memory-of-the-world/register/full-list-of-registered-heritage/registered-heritage-page-8/song-of-the-nibelungs-a-heroic-poem-from-mediaeval-europe/#c183708	
R4	2018	Bobbin lacemaking in Slovenia	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/bobbin-lacemaking-in-slovenia-01378	Replicators did not provide feedback about intangible heritage
	2017	Door-to-door rounds of Kurenti	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/door-to-door-rounds-of-kurenti-01278	
	2016	Škofja Loka passion play	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/skofja-loka-passion-play-01203	
R5	2019	Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock along migratory routes in the Mediterranean and in the Alps	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-along-migratory-routes-in-the-mediterranean-and-in-the-alps-01470	The only intangible Confirmed by Replicators
	2018	Art of dry stone walling, knowledge and techniques	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393	
	2016	Falconry, a living human heritage	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/falconry-a-living-human-heritage-01209	
	2013	Mediterranean diet	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884	
R6	2019	Traditional Turkish archery	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/traditional-turkish-archery-01367	
	2013	Turkish coffee culture and tradition	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/turkish-coffee-culture-and-tradition-00645	
	2012	Mesir Macunu festival	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mesir-macunu-festival-00642	

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	2011	Ceremonial Keşkek tradition	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/ceremonial-keskek-tradition-00388
	2010	Traditional Sohbet meetings	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/traditional-sohbet-meetings-00385
	2009	Karagöz	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/karagoz-00180
	2008	Arts of the Meddah, public storytellers	https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/arts-of-the-meddah-public-storytellers-00037

2.3 Main obstacles of the data gathering process

The process of acquiring data and material from RMs and Rs has presented several obstacles. On one hand, obstacles were due to difficulties encountered by RMs and Rs in accomplishing the task, mostly due to missing data and available knowledge. On the other hand, this data gathering process and method has led to a lack of homogeneity of data provided, including unsuitable formats. To solve the first type of barrier, the process of data gathering has been facilitated at all stages by providing tailored support to RMs and Rs through incrementing bilateral and collective communication and meetings, both remote (through bilateral skype sections and SIB/Replicator Forum remote meetings) and face to face (in conjunction project meetings and workshops). The direct and constant contact with RMs and Rs asking for specific assistance and support made more effective and successful the data gathering process and solved doubts and problems arisen.

Nevertheless, the process has been long and not all the required information has been provided. The not homogeneous response has been ascribed to the diversity of areas analysed and/or the different partners representative of those areas, having access to different sources of information. Capitalizing on the richness of such a diversity, members of POLITO proceeded to harmonize the data provided through the desk research performed at data analysis and processing stage. The POLITO team has consequently taken on the formats and the accuracy for the Atlas by filling further information.

Here below we provide a detailed description of such obstacles/difficulties and related corrective measures that have been provided to facilitate the process:

- **Need to select the data to be provided/visualized.** In some cases, such as RM1 Camino de Santiago, the extension of the area of interest and the huge amount of cultural and natural features available in the area represented a challenging issue. Listing and pointing all the relevant buildings, CH elements and other requirements in such case resulted to be a very long process and not really useful for the purpose of the mapping. Considering this, we asked to RMs and Rs to select the most relevant features and element and to include in the analysis and mapping visualization just a reduced amount of them. The criteria beyond this selection has been to give priority to those elements coherent with RURITAGE project and objectives, particularly relevant according to SIA and responding to RMs and Rs representatives interest and priorities.
- **Lack of experience on technical aspects.** Considering that some of the RMs did not answer to all the requests included in the first campaign, the second campaign also repeated in a simpler way some of the already asked questions. In order to avoid repetitions, we asked to RMs that had already provided the required information in the first campaign to disregard already answered questions. In case of RMs that did not answer to the first campaign at all – due to internal issues – as well as in case of RM7 that joined the project at M10 and of all the Rs, we asked them to complete only the winter campaign, in order to avoid confusion and repetition of tasks.
- **Difficulty in providing historical and technical full description of the quality of the attached**

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documentation. The main obstacle in the gathering the asked information was the difficulty for all RMs to provide specific historical information and technical full description on the quality of the attached documentation. Some details (authors, title, subject, date, copyright, typology, scale, owner/repository, format, link, author and additional information) were too complex or too specific. Solicitations and bilateral meetings on remote allow to overcome this obstacle.

- **Impossibility to have access and provide cadastral information.** In this specific case, the lack of a coherent information made it necessary to abandon to gather these data. In fact, it was not possible to achieve a common result to the wide range of different legislation of the RMs and Rs countries allowing a different availability of cadastral data (no open access, partial and/or temporal access, and/or by fee). This diversity and limited availability of information have been considered as a gap preventing to achieve a harmonised comparable information (both form the historical and current point of view).

For this reason, the decision was made to use a NoSQL database (not relational DB) that provides more flexibility when the data used are quite different among themselves.

3. Data processing: analysis and interpretation

3.1 Data analysis objectives and methodology: from raw data to processed data

The gathered data have been georeferenced and mapped according to an integrated data management. The desk review has processed raw disharmonious and discontinuous data provided by RMs and Rs, moving towards harmonized data suitable to shape information to be included and visualized in the RURITAGE Atlas. It consisted in analysing the data received, while creating a general overview of RMs and Rs features by performing additional research to enrich data and complete the information provided. Desk research started at data gathering stage to check the availability of more information about data and documentation provided, and it continued at data analysis and processing stage for the accuracy of the Atlas contents.

Moreover, the boundaries areas defined by co-mapping the perimeter of influence each RMs/Rs was checked to guarantee the coherence with geographical information and literature. The documentation was also processed in order to satisfy the qualitative criteria and standard format quality. It consists of recent and historical pictures, videos, audio-videos, maps, thematic maps, topographical maps, textual materials. Further information was finally added by desk review to complete the data provided.

The data analysis objectives have included aspects of **sensitive data and copyright** (see paragraph 3.3).

As a second step, all features identified were processed in order **to allow a comparative perspective** in the ATLAS. Data were processed to extract categories for the data management in the aim of meeting the RURITAGE challenges. In this aim not only the characterisation of each SIA, and more specifically of each RMs/Rs landscape, was brought out but also, at the same time, their cross-cutting features.

The analyses of Rs data was more articulated, according to the additional questions they were asked to fulfil. It has been aimed to enlighten and make understandable some lack or malfunctions of features in the rural areas. For this purpose, Rural/Urban interactions were especially analysed, as well as the accessibility of rural area, and the infrastructural gates and hubs, some gaps creating a disturbance in the Rs landscape perception and exploitation. Data of periodical events were processed in order to bring out information about time dynamics of the rural area changes and uses.

The data of RMs and Rs were finally processed in order to extract the **characterisations** and the **anatomy** for each RMs and Rs of to be combined with the features Conceptualisation and attributes Clustering of **RURITAGE Territories, Rural Contexts, and RURAL/URBAN interactions** (see Table 1.).

As a result, this process produced the layers that can be visualized in the ATLAS by identifying the main

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categories according to the Atlas objective of enhancing the knowledge of intangible and tangible features of RURITAGE territories. The features of the **Rural Regions, Rural Contexts, Rural Buildings, and the features that enlighten the Rural and Urban interaction as well as the boundaries areas were analysed.**

TABLE 6 LIST OF LAYERS

RURITAGE Territories	RMs /Rs area
	AREA OF INFLUENCE OF THE RM/R
	LAND USE (Agricultural, Industrial/commercial, Residential)
	SITES OF INTEREST (Heritage Sites, Archaeological Remains, Natural Sites Historical Settlements, Other Relevant Sites)
	NATURAL RISKS ZONES
	INFRASTRUCTURES AND FACILITIES (Transport Hubs, Transport Main Roads/Railways, Public facilities (Education, Hospitals, Municipal building)
	BUILDINGS (Protected Buildings, Buildings with Peculiar Functions For Pilgrims/Migrants Hospitality, Other Relevant Buildings)
Rural Contexts	ELEMENTS OF DISTURBANCE AND INTERFERENCE (refers to Replicators)
	OPEN AIR ACTIVITIES (Open Air Markets) TEMPORARY/PERIODICAL ROUTES (includes Pilgrimage and other routes)
	EVENTS (includes Festival) TEMPORARY/PERIODICAL
	MAIN CHANGES (includes Gentrification)
	TOURISM INFO POINT
	LINKS TO OTHER INFO
	TRADITIONAL MUSIC
TRADITIONAL DANCE	
RURAL/URBAN Interactions	NEARBY URBAN AREAS
	RELEVANT BUILDINGS IN NEARBY URBAN AREAS
	RELEVANT BUILDINGS IN NEARBY URBAN AREAS

This interpretation of data gathered and analysed has been presented at the RURITAGE community in the Insights from the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem at the occasion of Crete workshop.

LEVEL OF DATA ANALYSIS, MAPPING AND GEO-REPRESENTATION

Figure 3 Level of data analysis, mapping and geo-representation

Detailed information will be also available by queries about

- the nature of the Heritage declaration (World Site/European/National/Local)
- the seasonal activities

These Clusters have been addressed to a guided research in the database and a more user-friendly navigation of the ATLAS for visualizing each RM and Rs. After the First Period Review a new access to data has been shaped and, accordingly, to clustered data. While the previous Clusters were related to the data gathered, the new CLUSTERS frame the use of the information by the users.

For this purpose, 4 Clusters have been identified to make more easily understandable how the information available and how to find it in the ATLAS. The 4 Clusters PLACES, EXPERIENCES, TERRITORY; STORIES (see Table XXX in the chapter 5)

3.2 Data processing, analysis and interpretation main obstacle

Although the questionnaires addressed both tangible and intangible features of rural territories, the most relevant quantity of the processed data referred to tangible heritage, more specifically to buildings. The issue has been thus to manage these data by considering the finalisation of the RURITAGE Project.

The difficulties in identifying activities and functions in rural assets were possibly due that the requests to identify intangible aspects of the landscape are more unusual. Data about buildings, protected or for relevant functions, have been strongly mentioned and were easier to link to a

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mapping purpose. Information about these buildings could be also found and completed by desk work. Instead, events, routes, and peculiar functions for hospitality were more hard to find for enriching the data gathered by data desk research.

Furthermore, some corrective actions were needed. The collaborative mapping could include some randomness in the collected visual materials. The choice of attaching some specific documentation by RMs and Rs could also be due to its availability easier than other. To this aim, the desk review was

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important in order to avoid misunderstandings. The numerousness or vice versa the lack of visual materials, in fact, could create an ambiguous communication and consequently a wrong perception of rural assets features.

3.3 Data and copyright management

The questionnaires were delivered via mail. A specific account Ruritage@polito.it was expressly activated by POLITO in the aim to establish a direct and continuous desk service for the exchanges with RMs and Rs.

Raw data and material received through the dedicated mail have been uploaded and stored in the Ruritage Sharepoint, accomplishing data management requirements. All other copies of material and data received have been destroyed. Raw data and material will be made available for consultation in the Ruritage Open Repository (Zenodo).

Personal data management

No personal or sensitive data have been collected during the campaign, apart from Name, Surname and contact of RMs and Rs responsible for delivering material. This information will be not made available or public in the Atlas.

Data ownership and copyright management

During both campaigns, specific information have been asked to RMs and Rs for assessing the copyright and ownership status of the material provided (maps, photos, videos and other documentation). The answers can be reconducted to the following 3 cases:

- a. In most of the cases the owner of the material provided are RMs and Rs or other local stakeholders involved in the project;
- b. In other cases, the copyright owner is a third part;
- c. In other cases, the material is open access without copyright.

In a. and b. cases we proceed by circulating a “CopyRight Licence” (see Annex IV) that is being signed by the material owners. We disregard material whose ownership was not specified.

A new updated version of the “Copyright License” has been produced and signed by the material owners (see Annex IV).

4. The Atlas architecture: mapping, definition of data representation, data management and visualization

4.1 The Atlas architecture concept

The Atlas structure has been shaped according to the holistic approach of the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem, which inspired a synthetic and interconnected data representation and management. The Atlas includes georeferenced information, a digital archive, a digital library, and can be explored by navigating the map or by entries organised in a menu.

All data collected have been linked to each RM and R territory by georeferencing them in the ATLAS map. Georeferenced data refer to physical features and intangible contexts of the RURITAGE Territories. Following this approach, they have been organised by two main layers - RURITAGE Territories and Rural Contexts – each of them containing sub-layers. They identify the structure of the Atlas georeferenced database.

Moreover, the ATLAS also stores the visual, audio and textual documentation received from RMs and Rs as well as searched as desk works. This documentation has been organised, linked to each RM/R territory and collected into digital archives.

Apart from the data mapped and its archive, the Atlas also offers visual narratives. By using the data collected as a starting point, these narratives have been developed as a new elaboration and provide interpretations of the RURITAGE territories, features and contexts.

The data georeferenced amount to more than 1,800 items.

The platform has been designed by using mainly:

- Flask, a web framework written in Python
- the Javascript library called “Leaflet”, which allowed georeferenced data to be manipulated
- MongoDB, a NoSQL database using JSON-like documents

A more complex inquiry system of Atlas usage, such as multiple-choice research, and Atlas narratives creation will be developed through the implementation of the RURITAGE platform in the next months, to be delivered with the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem (D 5.3).

4.2 Georeferenced system mapping

The georeferenced system has initially been developed by using QGIS free open source system. It is composed of a list of Layers consisting of points, polygons or lines on the map and each of them is composed of several Attributes. Here below is a summary of the structure (see Annex II).

Atlas georeferenced database structure– Layers:

- 1) **RMS /RS AREA** (polygon): It refers to the main area of each RM and R. Its attributes identify the main characterization of the area, including documentation about the site (such as the most recent and the oldest cadastral maps; digital inventories; videos, phone applications, etc.).
- 2) **INFLUENCE_AREA** (polygon): It refers to the influence area of each RM and R according to the SIA they belong to (pilgrimage, sustainable food production, migration, art&festival, resilience, landscape).
- 3) **LAND_USE** (polygon): It refers to the functional distribution of land and land use within RM and R area. Its attributes identify and describe, among others, the type of functions and production (agriculture, industrial, commercial, residential, touristic, public, etc).
- 4) **SITE** (polygon): It refers to any site characterising the RMs and Rs territories, such as heritage sites, archaeological remains, natural sites, and historical settlements, and areas under the risk of natural disasters. Its attributes identify and describe the legal registration status of the site (UNESCO, national conservation area, local conservation area, not registered etc); the status of master/conservation/management plan (planned, continuing, historical, recent); the type of site (gorge, lake, falls, park, mining site, park, settlement, village, archaeological site, rural production site, craft production site, vineyard, altar, crossing, statue, beauty spot, asset, monument, archaeological remains), the level of popularity of the site (recently popular, historic, in literature, in media, traditional storytelling) and other information.
- 5) **INFRASTR** (polygon): it refers to relevant infrastructural elements within RM and R area. Its attributes identify, among others, the infrastructure's category (transport, water, electricity, sewage/canalization, energy, public service); the infrastructure's type (highway, street, trail, square, travel hub, bridge, railway, railway station, long-distance bus station, river, canal, wind/solar energy source, municipality, hospital).
- 6) **BUILDINGS** (point): it refers to monuments, historic buildings, and other significant buildings within RM and R area. Its attributes identify and describe the function (museum, religious, governmental, residential, public, commercial, residential, industrial, military, tourism); the building type (city hall, priesthood, centre, castle, chapel, shelter, monastery, church, complex, prison, palace, museum, hermitage, tower, house, barn, jurisdictional roll, washtub, cell, mill, observatory, bath, farm); if the building is a heritage asset, if the building is rehabilitated, the reason for rehabilitation (cultural activities, activities related to art and festival, migrants hospitality, public authority headquarters, tourism, private uses), rehabilitation date/temporal frame; the status of conservation (planned, continuing, historical, recent); and other info such as the building date, the architect, etc.
- 7) **ELEMENTS OF DISTURBANCE AND INTERFERENCE** (point): it refers to elements of disturbance within R areas. Its attributes identify the type of elements: telecommunication (base stations for mobile phones, radios, TVs); transportation (highways, canals, tunnels); technological (gas pipeline, power plant); electrical infrastructural elements (electric cables, poles); implantation

for renewable energy (solar panels, photovoltaics, wind farms); instalment of elements potentially movable that change the perception of the landscape (large advertisement panels, large LCD screens, etc); commercial, industrial or agricultural settlements with their services; quarries (active, underused, dismissed); waste facilities (active, underused, dismissed); attraction areas (amusement parks, camping/picnic areas); buildings or groups of buildings that affect the character of the landscape (e.g. sprawl); new buildings that contrast with the cultural natural landscape because of typology, color, material, decontextualization; improper street pavement (asphalt in natural area, improper finishing); recurrent collective events that contrast with the landscape (carousel, circus); new collective events that contrast with the landscape (e.g. parties).

- 8) **OPEN_AIR** (polygon): it refers to relevant open-air activities within RM and R area. Its attributes identify and describe, among others, the temporal frame/periodicity and seasonality of the activities, the type (open air markets, weekly or monthly antiquities markets, etc., cultural activities, etc.).
- 9) **ROUTE** (line): it refers mainly to pilgrimage itineraries within RM and R area. Its attributes identify and describe also the type of itinerary (religious/natural/historical etc.); the legal registration status of the itinerary; the status of the conservation/management plan; relevant temporal frame; buildings/sites/towns of the itinerary and related characterization/description.
- 10) **EVENT** (point): it refers to relevant large events (such as festivals that take place in multiple locations within the RM and R area). Its attributes identify the name of the events, the type of the event (art, cultural, food and wine, natural, brand creation, development project, economic agreement, delimitation of protected area, other); temporal frame/date/seasonality; description of the event and other information.
- 11) **CHANGE** (polygon): it refers to areas interested by changes, that suffered destruction processes etc. Its attributes identify and describe, among others, the type of change occurred (World War II, other wars, urban projects, disasters, international events such as EXPOs/Olympics), and the temporal frame/date.
- 12) **TOURISM** (point): it refers to tourism related buildings/kiosks/info points within RM and R area. Its attributes identify their type (tourist information, information panel, etc) and other info.
- 13) **NEAR_URBAN_AREAS** (point): it refers to the closest urban area. Its attributes identify, among others, the name and numbers of closest urban areas and the existing relation between the RM/R rural area and the identified urban area (no relevant relation, if the rural area is self-sufficient; limited relation, if the relation is limited to bureaucratic processes and governance actions; intermediate relation, if residences go to urban areas for major needs such as hospitals, municipal registrations; strong relation, if majority of residences go to urban areas on a daily basis).

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- 14) **N_TOWN_BLDG** (point): it refers to buildings in nearby towns relevant accordingly to rural regeneration process. Its attributes identify, among others, the type of buildings (cultural organization, educational, local authority, public service, infrastructural); their legal registration status and other information.
- 15) **N_RELEVANT_FUNCTIONS** (points): it refers to relevant infrastructural buildings in the closest urban areas that increase the dependence of RM and R on the closest urban areas. Its attributes identify, among others, the infrastructure's category (transport, water, electricity, sewage/canalization, energy, public service); the infrastructure's type (highway, street, trail, square, travel hub, bridge, railway, railway station, long-distance bus station, river, canal, wind/solar energy source, municipality, hospital).

More than 1,800 tangible and intangible features have been mapped; while the highest numerosity refers to the tangible assets, many other important functions and activities are also included.

The final data have been stored in a JSON-like format (GeoJSON). Each feature stored in the Atlas corresponds to an object with a structure of this format. Each object has a list of record of the type key/value: to each key, represented by a word that is unique inside the object, corresponds a value that may be a word, a number or a list of words/numbers. This kind of format has been chosen for 2 main reasons: it is a standard GIS software and is easily manageable from the tool we use to display the map and the features. Using this data format, we stored more than 1,200 buildings, 300 sites, 10 areas affected by changes, 100 infrastructures, 50 open air activities, 20 itineraries, 30 tourist information points with the relative associated information.

4.3 Development of the Atlas creative mapping: data management and visualization

The data representation, management and visualization of the “creative mapping” have had as objective the fully rich and user-friendly approach to the data access through the end-users interacting with the ATLAS.

After the first period review the visualization have been improved. ATLAS allows visualizing the georeferenced data in different kind of maps (Open street map, Satellite view, Open Topo map, Relieve map). This improved visualization also enables to grasp new kind of information. The topographic maps are especially coherent with RURITAGE Atlas aim. They display the georeferenced data in the context of topographical views of territories by making understandable the physical layers of the landscape and highlighting the natural elements and local specificities of rural areas.

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The platform allows for navigation of, and enquiry to the ATLAS providing for exploration and understanding of the RM and R landscapes and their “anatomy”:

- i. By navigating, data can be directly accessed and visualized via interaction with the points and symbols on the map. This option allows the territory of each RM and R to be visualized directly with its boundary. The mapped features are progressively visualized through icons on the map according to focus and the detailed scale of the screen.
- ii. By enquiry, data organized into a database can be questioned through menus. In this case the menus allow the RM and R territories to be linked, and also for cross-cutting research through the mapped layers.

According to the layers and attributes organized into the database many queries are available. Furthermore, the platform allows for the visualization of a rich documentation illustrating and narrating

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the RM and R territories and features. All the audio-visual-textual materials provided have been organized into digital archives by referring to each RM and R. The archives have been made accessible through the menus.

Moreover, the Atlas also includes RURITAGE newly-created audio-visual-textual materials representing narratives of readings of RM and R landscapes. They are constituted of 3D models and BIM for underlining the R features according to RURITAGE strategies. Troubadour pictures, as well as pictures coming from the digital MyCult Rural Toolkit will be included in the database. The digital MyCult-Rural Toolkit (developed as part of Task 4.4) designed to help build capacity within the communities of Replicator sites to monitor and evaluate the success of actions/projects will be linked to the Atlas. It consists of two Apps ('Rate my View' and 'Landscape Connect') and the Tagscape methodology. The georeferenced images and text uploaded via the Apps will be filtered and displayed within the Atlas. Audio-videos also will be included with the aim of creating narratives by extracting SIA landscape capitals through insights into the collected data and documentation. All narratives are made accessible through digital libraries referred to each RM and R.

Figure 4 Atlas Architecture

Following the Atlas Concept and the Mapping Layers, the Atlas entries criteria were conceived. The Atlas allows, in fact, navigating and entry by menus. The entries are conceived for visualizing data and inquiry. The menus offer the possibility to focus both on each RM and R, or on crosscutting features.

TABLE 7 ENTRY CRITERIA

MENU SIAss	∅	RURITAGE SIAs info visualisation	
MENU RMs	∅	Link to navigate the territory	
	∅	Link to the DIGITAL ARCHIVE menu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ maps ✓ pictures ✓ videos
MENU Rs	∅	Link to navigate the territory	
	∅	Link to the DIGITAL ARCHIVE menu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ maps ✓ pictures ✓ videos
	∅	Link to the DIGITAL NARRATIVES menu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 3D models ✓ BIM ✓ RURITAGE videos ✓ RURITAGE TROUBADOUR/Rate My View
MENU FEATURES	∅	RURITAGE Territories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RMs /Rs area ✓ AREA OF INFLUENCE OF THE RM/R ✓ LAND USE (Agricultural, Industrial/commercial, Residential) ✓ PROTECTED SITES (Heritage Sites, Archaeological Remains, Natural Sites Historical Settlements) ✓ NATURAL RISKS ZONES ✓ INFRASTRUCTURES AND FACILITIES (Transport Hubs, Transport Main Roads/Railways, Public facilities (Education, Hospitals, Municipal building)) ✓ BUILDINGS (Protected Buildings, Buildings With Peculiar Functions For Pilgrims/Migrants Hospitality, Other Relevant Buildings) ✓ ELEMENTS OF DISTURBANCE AND INTERFERENCE (refers to Replicators)
	∅	Rural Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ OPEN AIR ACTIVITIES (Open Air Markets) TEMPORARY/PERIODICAL ✓ ROUTES (include Pilgrimage and other routes) ✓ EVENTS (include Festival) TEMPORARY/PERIODICAL ✓ MAIN CHANGES (include Gentrification) ✓ TOURISM INFO POINT ✓ LINKS TO OTHER INFO ✓ TRADITIONAL MUSIC ✓ TRADITIONAL DANCE
	∅	RURAL/URBAN Interactions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEARBY URBAN AREAS ✓ RELEVANT BUILDINGS IN NEARBY URBAN AREAS ✓ RELEVANT FUNCTIONS (Transport infrastructures, Public facilities)

Figure 5 Entries Menu Criteria first release

After the first period review, a new graphical user interface (GUI) has been developed which enables a new kind of research in the ATLAS for querying and visualizing features contextually (see chapter 5).

A new functionality also allows visualizing for the Replicators the related KPI by connecting the ATLAS with the monitoring platform.

The Key Performance Indicator (KPI) evaluated by Cartif in task x.x have been partially integrated inside the Atlas. When the user click on the icon of one of the replicators, in addition to the main information regarding its territories, he can also see two gauge graphs. This graphs show the performance of the selected Replicator, as calculated by

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Cartif, at the beginning of the project and after one year to evaluate how much the regeneration process fostered by the Ruritage strategies has influenced.

According to the identified criteria, the Atlas architecture has been structured as shown by the following screenshots:

RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem
Heritage for Rural Regeneration

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 776465.

Figure 6 Ruritage Resource Ecosystem overview

RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem
Heritage for Rural Regeneration

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 776465.

Figure 7 Atlas Overview

Figure 8a Atlas Navigation with Legend

Figure 8b Atlas inquiries RMs

Figure 8c Atlas inquiries Rs

Figure 9 Atlas inquiry by R search in the new release with the visualization of KPI

4.4 Visual narratives

The RURITAGE Atlas includes digital libraries for visual narratives:

- 3D models
- Pictures and Audio-Visual came from MyCult Rural Toolkit (Rate my View and Landscape Connect) and RURITAGE Troubadour.

Here below, 3D models produced for two replicators are presented. They have been generated by adopting different approaches and softwares to represent different scales and features. The models are produced with a purpose to provide a tool for the valorization of replicators territories. Two replicators, R5 (Appignano) and R6 (Izmir) have been selected to present model pilot.

These visual narratives have been integrated in the historical Cultural Natural Heritage narratives according to the new GUI (see chapter 5)

4.4.1 3D modelling for Appignano del Tronto replicator

The 3D modelling and data visualization aim have been producing a series of models to document the state of the urban area of Appignano del Tronto before and after the earthquake and the subsequent controlled demolitions of the damaged buildings. 3D model visualization will be a useful tool able to compare the previous buildings no more extant and the approved projects of the same areas that have yet to be built. 3D models will be implemented on a digital web-based platform (Atlas) developed for the RURITAGE project, where it will be possible to consult and visualize the 3D digital contents and additional textual and/or graphical information linked to the georeferenced models. The case study of Appignano del Tronto has to be considered as a preliminary reference case that will define a series of standards that are going to be adopted by the other projects that will eventually be uploaded on the platform, thus the

next sections will describe all the tests that have been carried out to be able to achieve the best results, despite all the criticalities that web-based applications may arise.

Figure 10 Appignano del Tronto

According to the final outcomes of the project, the 3D model of the historical centre of Appignano del Tronto has been produced with Rhinoceros by NURBS modelling, then the polysurfaces were converted into discretized meshes, in order to implement them within ATLAS web platform, as textured models. With this approach it was possible to vary the segmentation/discretization of the model only at the end of the modelling process which maximises its versatility, because in this way it is possible to precisely control the relation between of polygon number of each model and the overall accuracy according to the general aims of the RURITAGE project. Accurate models, in fact, with a low number of polygons are especially important for web applications or real time visualizations for architecture.

Figure 11 Appignano del Tronto damaged building

4.4.2 3D modelling in Urban Scale for Izmir replicator

As an alternative approach, an urban 3D model will be defined in RURITAGE based on the CityGML standard using Izmir case study. This model will consist of the graphical representation of urban elements and their semantics. 3D model is represented by buildings with level of detail LoD2 (see Figure 12). Properties included in the model contain information belonging to the core of CityGML and other properties not included that have required the extension of CityGML for the representation of the cultural heritage.

Figure 12 LoDs in CityGML

The information required to generate the 3D urban model is divided into information to generate the geometry, information about the properties (minimum necessary use, age, height and protection), information for heights and delimitation of the environment. The required information and the format in the following table are presented below:

TABLE 8 REQUIRED DATA FOR URBAN 3D MODEL GENERATION

REQUIRED INFORMATION	DATA FORMAT
Delimitation of the environment	SHP or IMAGE

Geometric representation of building footprints	SHP
Representative characteristics of each building	SHP or XLS (referenced to SHP)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main use - Year of construction - Protection degree - Height 	
DSM – Digital Surface Model (if height not included)	ASC or CSV
DTM – Digital Terrain Model (if height not included)	ASC or CSV

It is necessary to collect the identified data sources. The data collected is pre-processed as a preliminary step to the generation of the urban 3D model. This pre-processing allows to eliminate erroneous data, duplicated data and others from outside the area of interest. LiDAR data is also filtered limiting the delimitation of the environment and semantic information from different sources is combined into a single information file.

For the geometric generation of the model the process presented in the following figure is implemented (see Figure 13). The data sources available in GIS (SHP) format are processed and combined to obtain the most accurate floor-scale geometry at the building scale. In addition, the digital surface model (DSM) and the digital terrain model (DTM) are processed to obtain the estimated building heights. This information allows the geometric generation of the 3D model in CityGML format with level of detail LoD2 for the buildings in the area.

Figure 13 Urban 3D model generation process

As a result of the process of generating the urban 3D model, a CityGML model is obtained and the geometry of the model in KML format, which allows visualization in the Google Earth platform.

The village of Yukaribey was selected to build the 3D model since there is located the Rural Heritage Hub (RHH) from the Izmir replicator and the model can support the decision making regarding the regeneration strategies. The 3D model of a selected group of buildings close to the RHH has been generated based on the process described above (see Figure 1). 3D urban model has been used for the energy assessment of the modelled buildings. For this task the process presented in the next figure (see Figure 2) has been followed.

Figure 14 CityGML 3D Model of Yukaribey

The first step of the process provides detailed geometry at building scale (GIS files with the geometry) and semantic information associated with that geometry. This step required fieldwork. The information collected from the data sources was processed to get the relevant information needed for the analysis of energy demand. In order to achieve a high level of detail and reliability for the input data, it is necessary to carry out a process of adaptation, cleaning and organization of the existing data. Then, several automatic geospatial analyses allow calculating or estimating new data at building envelope level, that are relevant for energy assessment (envelope area and orientation). The result is a 3D model which combines the information contained in the original SHP, the data captured in the fieldwork and the new calculated and estimated data.

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GIS DATA

Figure 15 Energy Assessment at urban scale based on GIS3D

The next step in the process is the energy demand assessment. The method used for calculating the energy demand applied at urban scale is based on the ISO_13790. This method is the result of an international consensus of renowned institutions and it has been successfully tested in several European countries, even based on data from multi-scale urban models. The amount of data required is low, although the level of detail provided for the model is at the level of the building envelope, considering values by orientation for each of the elements of the envelope (facades, adjoining walls, roof and ground). The climatic data is completed with monthly average values that are obtained from climate files from the city or a nearby one (e.g. EnergyPlus).

The results obtained from the energy assessment at urban scale are visualized through a GIS3D interface (see Figures 3 and 4). The GIS3D visualization is based on the multiscale CityGML model described previously. This model is used to calculate the energy assessment and to visualize the results. The tool offers a web visualization based on GIS 3D that shows the characteristics of each building and the spatial distribution of the most representative building parameters and the energy demand calculated (total and by square meter).

Figure 16 GIS-3D Viewer of Yukaribey 3D Model showing main material of buildings

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Figure 17 GIS-3D Viewer of Yukaribey showing geospatial distribution of heating demand of buildings and information of the selected building

4.4.3 3D modelling for Historic Market in Izmir replicator

The 3D model for the replicator 'Izmir Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins' is generated for the historic Ottoman bazaar ('arasta' in Turkish) in the site (Bergama, Izmir). This area is selected together with the replicator and the Bergama municipality due to the ongoing regeneration project targeting the bazaar. In addition, it is aimed to communicate information regarding the relation of the bazaar with the landscape morphology as well as the archaeological site Pergamon (which is located on the top of the hill with a strong visual relationship with the city). The final product will be stored at and presented through Ruritage Resource Ecosystem as a part of ATLAS where the users will be able to consult, visualize, navigate, and get informed regarding the area in a georeferenced structure with relation to the larger area in landscape scale.

Figure 18 Bergama site

The model is produced utilizing photographs of the buildings on each building block, 2D architectural façade drawings in AutoCAD software, and the master plan of the city in the AutoCAD software. The Bergama Municipality and the replicator (Izmir Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins) provided these materials through collaboration with the POLITO team.

For the 3D model of the bazaar, Autodesk Revit software was used due to its compatibility with the AutoCAD software and its flexibility to convert the model to other formats. In addition to the structures, the topographic model of the bazaar is also produced based on the information extracted from the master plan. The Revit software also provided the possibility to present detailed information including the construction techniques and materials when necessary. Thus, the main aim of producing the model is both to show the relationship of the bazaar with the larger territory and to present information about the bazaar in the building scale.

Figure 19 Model in detail 4.5 Data mapping, management and visualisation main obstacles

4.5 Data mapping, management and visualisation main obstacles

The main obstacle was related to the web georeferenced system to be used for mapping and linking all data. This obstacle was mainly related to the multiple use of the ATLAS platform that was required to be complementary to the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem in order to visualize and link the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) and the RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learned (D1.2) and, if necessary, further documentation (Troubadours and My Cult-Rural toolkit outputs which include georeferenced images and text uploaded via the Apps).

In the first stage of the Atlas development, the ARCHES platform was adopted. A mock-up was shaped with the aim of checking data management and visualization. According to the data gathered scheduled, both for the mapping and for the Repository, the ARCHES platform was experimented with in the late Autumn with the partial data collected in the first campaign between October and January. These preliminary tests were very important in shaping the best ATLAS architecture for the RURITAGE project. On the one hand, the system offered poor possibilities to visualize the RURITAGE challenges. In fact, it was recognised that the ARCHES platform was not flexible enough for new different developments and required too many redefinitions to be combined with the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem. Although the data gathered could easily be mapped and visualized, it proved very difficult and time-consuming to move away from the standard visualization provided by the system.

Furthermore, another issue was that the usage of this platform would have required end-users to have at least a basic knowledge of GIS, while RURITAGE project methodology requires a user-friendly interface to be used by people with no technical background. The Atlas, in fact, will be made available for RM/R interaction according to the RURITAGE implementation for which it was conceived.

Having considered these difficulties, it was judged infeasible to persist with this system. Another system of data representation, therefore, needed to be developed from scratch, and following up on this we were able to have more freedom in customizing the platform to meet our needs.

However, this change implied a considerable expenditure of time by requiring us, in fact, to move all data onto the new platform. The data migration could not be handled entirely mechanically because of the differences between the ARCHES database (PostgreSQL) and the newly-adopted platform. All data georeferenced and consolidated still needed to be georeferenced and inserted again. Moreover, the new web platform also necessitated the development of a graphical interface and a new concept in visualizing and questioning the Atlas.

5. User-friendliness of the ATLAS

After the first period of review, a specific analysis and development of ATLAS **user-friendliness** has been strengthened. This study consists of an analysis of weakness, a literature review, improvement of the usability of the functions, new tool's modalities, new modeled information and, finally, an additional graphical user interface (GUI). As a result, this report provides a new release of the ATLAS.

Although this release closes the task of the development of the ATLAS creative mapping, the team will continue to work for implementing The ATLAS in parallel with RURITAGE project developments. These new developments of the ATLAS will be delivered with the Deliverable 5.3 (M. 36).

Furthermore, as it has been pointed out by the report (chapter 1), in fact, the ATLAS is not only a Web-GIS but also a component of the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystems. While the creative mapping, its interface and related functionalities are a component of the architecture of the Ecosystem and the integration of its tools. This task is still under development . The final version will be provided with the Deliverable 5.3 (M. 36).

As a general introduction it should be noted that the development of the ATLAS requires several different expertise. The group of developers' expertise include cultural heritage and cultural landscapes, digital history of the environment, the territory and the architecture, ICTs, geomatics, 3d modelling. The development thus requires strong synergies and interactions among researchers.

The last months have strongly compromised this interaction. The COVID crisis has made impossible to work together in a laboratory. Meetings in remote have made possible to discuss some aspects, but not really to build together the various components. This condition has made more difficult the interdisciplinary approach.

On one hand, the technical components have been quite difficult to manage as it requires high performant hardware that are not the personal computer owned by the researchers. The machines for this kind of work were located at the university with any access in the lockdown period and later as well as currently was limited.

On the other hand, similar issues also refer to the survey for completing and checking the information. In particular, historical information, historical cartography and maps and pictures, were collected by desk research and a new campaign of data gathering specifically addressed to Replicators.

The participation to the creative co-mapping has been more active than to the campaigns at the beginnings of the ATLAS development. The parallel involvement of the Replicators in regeneration strategies has made more effective their involvement in the development of the ATLAS, too. Most Replicators have started to be more aware about its potential and play as leading actors in building the contents of the ATLAS Stories.

5.1 Verifying the user-friendliness

The ATLAS is an online open tool designed for the RURITAGE project, To access Atlas the user isn't required

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to be a member of the project neither the platform requires any user account.

By interacting with the graphical interface of the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem, the interface of the ATLAS appears when the user clicks on the ATLAS button.

The ATLAS interface shows the web-GIS map. The touch screen function enables users to zoom in/out. Alternatively, the signs +/- on the map facilitate the user in zooming in/out the map.

On the top of the interface, the user can easily identify three buttons that are clearly emphasized by the burnt orange color. The buttons introduce users to the main RURITAGE project matter with its specific glossary: Systemic Innovation Areas, Role Models, Replicators.

Each button opens a menu showing: (i) the 6 SIAs with its related icons, (ii) the 13 Role models and (iii) the 6 Replicators. The texts identifying RMs and Rs are all distinguished by the colors of the related SIA.

On a side of the screen two more buttons allow opening, vertically, a Keymap and a Navigation legend. The keymap is for not losing the orientation, when the user zooms in the ATLAS. The legend identifies the attributes of the mapped points, lines, and polygons. They refer to the identified features of these rural areas as explained above.

While users zoom in the map, the mapped information also emerges on the map. Mapped information is marked by icons according to the legend. The platform allows that by clicking on the icons on the map, a pop-up window provides specific information.

In theory, as developers of the tool, this procedure seemed us correct and effective. However, a **weakness** in this approach has been drawn to attention. Users can find complex the modality of navigating and searching for information.

By examining the reasons of this complexity, we have noticed that:

- the modality of zooming in for visualizing data doesn't arise in sufficient speed for real time adaptation.
- users visualize such a quantity of many different icons that a non-expert user can lose his/her interest
- by considering the quantity of data mapped in an area, the modality to access information by clicking on each icon can discourage a fully use of data mapped
- the search by features in the database isn't intuitive
- lack of fully visualization due to the lack of connection between the search for information in the database and the map

A macro-weakness seems due to the quantity of data that affects the real time adaptation of the map and makes it complex to navigate in the ATLAS basic functionality as well as to make queries in the related database.

The points of weakness, thus, has been deepened for evaluating how to improve user friendliness without losing information and modalities. Not only we didn't like to reduce the quantity of data mapped, in fact, but in the meantime, we were also working on adding new information.

The analysis of these weakness requested to reflect on the modeled information and its visualization, the tool's function and the GUI. In this aim, the literature review has been deepened.

In the recent years, the usage of GIS in the Cultural Heritage field has been rapidly increasing. Several Cultural Heritage studies and GIS-based applications have been developed for surveying and analyzing cultural data. We could consider that GIS as the main tool in use for analyzing **spatial data** in unprecedented numbers of aspects. GIS has been also combined with other visualization tools, such us 3D models, for improving the analysis' means and/or the understandability of cultural heritage among non-expert users. The purpose of this approach encompasses a wide range of topics and scopes. It includes the large sphere of Cultural Heritage studies, from the documentation, to the conservation, up to the promotion.

On the other hand, critical studies have experienced and analyzed how the use of digital environments can facilitate tools in Cultural Heritage for the inventory, evaluation, and preservation of historic sites. Studies on digital cultural heritage have especially pointed out on the impact of the digital tools in increasing the understanding and spreading the heritage as well as its impact in digital transformation.

By considering GIS approach to cultural data, two main aspects should be considered and verified in the case

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of the RURITAGE ATLAS to frame its user friendliness: the scale of the information and the nature of the mapped data.

The GIS, in fact, appears as a very useful tool for an overview encompassing the scale of a project as a whole. But it is effective only when it highlights a limited number of attributes.

The RURITAGE ATLAS is a large-scale project that include XXX countries and 19 territories among Role Models and Replicators that are clustered in the 6 Systemic Innovations Actions. GIS approach allows effectively visualizing this huge scale of RURITAGE project as a whole. The ATLAS, in fact, easily provides an intuitive overview of the large scale of the project for the interested rural territories and present the cluster system of RURITAGE project. The weakness then is rather in the visualization of a wide range of information.

An important aspect of the wealth of the mapped information refers to **the diversity of cultural forms and practices taken into account by the ATLAS**. This aspect reproduces the wealth of CNH in RURITAGE project. By analyzing the criteria that we used for mapping information, we confirm that the number and the quality of diverse territories of RURITAGE project (and the clustered in SIAs), with their different characterizations, need identifying several CNH categories. Moreover, RURITAGE approach and purpose also require a contextualization of the CNH to be understood in the rural regions with their physical dimension, their strengths and weak points for rural regeneration. A comparative perspective (RMs/Rs) requires combining the local specificities with the identifications of crosscutting features. Furthermore, the comparative perspective is also important under a critical point of a view as it reinforces CNH interpretative keys.

However, ATLAS focuses on Cultural Natural Heritage. According to the RURITAGE Project, the RMs and Rs mostly refer to **intangible heritage** and large-scale categories such as Geoparks, Cultural Routes, cultural landscapes, food. This specificity makes the use of **spatial data** and GIS approach more difficult than in the current uses of GIS and visualization tools that mostly focus on tangible heritage. This spatialization tools approach requires some reflections and adjustments for user-friendliness requirements.

The following step has been to move from a data collection focus to a fully user-centered approach. This purpose has required to improve, on one hand, the criteria for clustering data mapped and, on the other hand, the functionality by designing a new function of the platform for accessing and visualising the information mapped and stored in the ATLAS.

5.2 Planning userfriendly approaches

PLANNING USER FRIENDLY APPROACHES

INTENDED USERS	RMs, Rs, users interested in RURITAGE project and methodology, persons interested in cultural and natural heritage, investors, decisions makers
REQUIRED HARDWARE	Adaptable to different kind of devices
REQUIRED SOFTWARE AND OPERATING SYSTEM	User only needs an Internet browser (download of a software isn't needed)
REQUIRED SKILLS	Online tool, easy to use for non-expert users
TOOLS BENEFITS	Identify more relevant Cultural Natural Heritage within an overall overview of the RMs/Rs territories; Grasp a spatial and visual dimension of the area of interest and the area of effective/potential influence; overlook CNH main features in their geographical and historical contexts; Gain an understanding of accessibility, public services and facilities; Recognize the CNH as valuable benefit for developing rural regeneration strategies and the tool supports discussion and interaction among stakeholders

The ATLAS as an outcome of RURITAGE H2020 research project should achieve accuracy, reliability and user-friendliness as a result. A good balance between scientific approach and practical usability is needed to meet the wider interest of this purpose.

For the friendliness' aim, specific objectives have been defined. They are:

- 1) communicate the input of data assumptions to use the tool effectively in order that the tool outputs are understandable and easy to interpret
- 2) make more grasping and appealing the use of the tool through an interface more interactive and graphically attractive
- 3) design the tool adaptable to any kind of device and provide a function of the tool that performs a sufficient speed for real time adaptations
- 4) integrate the quality of the information
- 5) take into account future uses

As collectors and organizers of the information, this approach has required to move from an organized collection of data according to categories useful for scientific analysis to the user's perspective. In this aim, the interest of users in interacting with cultural natural heritage and the territories has been the baseline of the developed perspective.

To this purpose, a good meaningful example has been the approach of "Stories" developed by the Joint Research Center of Europe (JRC), to inform in an easily accessible way about several initiatives across Europe linked to cultural heritage. The Story Maps text and the maps have been released by the European Commission

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

at the occasion of the first ever European Cultural Heritage Summit, on 22 June 2018 in Berlin. They are a set of interactive maps to raise awareness of cultural heritage in Europe.

By analysing the tool, it is seen that the Story Maps are a GIS based project (ArcGIS software) displayed by a platform that allows visualize information. The graphical user interface is conceived as a double visualization that allows users browsing in parallel the related information as textual and visual.

In this aim we have conceived a new functionality for connecting the database and the map with clustered the information for each territory. This approach enabled both technical and conceptual improvements. Moreover, the web pages have been designed to be responsive.

Users will be able to make queries to the database and visualize in parallel the answer as a list and also in the map. This search by Rm/R is available for all mapped rural regions.

5.3 Oriented navigation of the ATLAS and user-friendly access to the database

The **user friendliness** purpose has been developed by improvements gained through more paths:

- a conceptual path, the achievement of which has been the prioritization of information for each RM/R to be accessed through 4 main entries. The entries displayed offer a choice among: **Places, Experiences, Territory, Stories**;
- a new function of the platform that allows connecting the research in the database with the visualization of the data in the map in parallel;
- an additional graphical user interface (GUI) that makes more intuitive to find what kind of information is available and to visualize heterogeneous data in the Atlas;
- a visual communication improvement through the development of historical CNH narratives;

The 4 main entries aim at users can immediately grasp the multidimensional layers of rural landscapes. They identify the articulated dimension of cultural natural heritage, both tangible (Places) and intangible (Experiences) in the rich scenarios of RURITAGE rural territories, (Territory) and make available all connected historical information, images, 3D models (Stories). These entries also integrate other external data (e.g. Natura 2000 sites, CORINE Land Cover data).

The data access framework has been specified according to the conceptual map shown below:

Figure 21 The conceptual map for the new access to data search

According to the above conceptual map, the shapefiles with the attributes of the GIS system have been re-addressed. The links are shown in the below conceptual map.

ATLAS (PREVIOUS VERSION)

Figure 22 Concordances between shapefiles and entries according to the new GUI

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

By building on the conceptual map a new coherent GUI has been developed for the queries in the database (Task 5.1). The GUI enables the function for search and visualize the answer in parallel in the database and in the map.

The new graphical user interface, thus, enables **an oriented navigation** of the ATLAS by a simplified user-friendly access to the database. The user through the 4 main entries can discover how to interact with CNH in the region and learn through visual and textual storytelling.

The new interface appears after selecting the **search function** visualized by a magnifying glass icon. The modality is enabled by selecting a Role Model or Replicator.

Each of the 4 main entries – Places, Experiences, Territory, Stories – includes more detailed choices that are displayed simultaneously on the screen. The user can points by a wide but oriented overview of possible choices for getting the information and visualising its related geolocalisation..

Figure 23 The new Graphical User Interface for search by features for RM/R

Figure 24 The new responsive webpage with the GUI displaying database search and map

More improvements of this function and a full integration with the tools in the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem will be made possible through the development of the platform architecture (T5.1, D XX). Guidelines and recommendation for the use of the ATLAS will be included in the RURITAGE Resource Ecosystem guidelines (T5.5 D XX).

Figure 25 Example of the search with the information displayed

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

Globasnitz/Globasnica, Feistritz ob Bleiburg/Bistrica nad Pilberkom, Bleiburg/Pilberk, Neuhaus, Lavamünd, Črna na Koroškem, Mežica, Prevalje, Ravne na Koroškem and Dravograd). For the development of the baseline, only 1 municipality (Globasnitz/Globasnica) has been considered, because is where the main Pilgrimage place is located.

Figure 26 Example of the search with the information displayed in parallel

5.4 Replicators' Historical Cultural Natural Heritage Narratives

The historical narratives create a focus on some points of highest cultural natural interest and its dynamics of changes from the Past to the current site. They also provide photos, historical iconography, 3D models and videos. Images and documentation have been collected with the participation of local stakeholders.

By considering the rich variety of Cultural Natural Heritage of RURITAGE RMs and Rs and their historical developments, a thoughtful choice was needed. This choice has been undertaken by taking into account the "Recommendations concerning future work", after the first Period Review that have underlined the need of a *more user-friendly and 'intuitive' usage regarding the future developments of the project.*

According to this recommendation, for this development we've agreed with the UNIBO to add information that could support and facilitate the regeneration process of the Replicators.

Furthermore, historical information has been also collected and new functions have been developed by creating user-friendly historical CNH narratives to be visualized in Atlas. The historical CNH narratives aim to highlight specific aspects of Rs cultural and natural heritage and history. The historical narratives topics have been discussed and agreed with UNIBO responsible for the rural regeneration strategies and the Replicators. In this aim a series of meeting have been held to shape the topics, collect relevant data and information. The participation of POLITO at the Replicators Forums have also allowed the general presentation and the following updates about the task.

The topics selected represent specific elements with high importance for the Replicators not only because of their historic value but also because connected with Replicators actions of their Regeneration Plans.

Several internal POLITO meetings have been needed for the cultural and technical development of the narratives and their visualization and of the modalities for the user interaction. A large multidisciplinary group of about 8 has collaborated.

The narratives have been organised in autonomous websites (with the software ADOBE MUSE) to be displayed by the platform. Each environment includes:

- Thematic Timeline
- 3 to 4 historical insights visualized through interactive visual and textual narratives
- 3D models expressly modelled for the ATLAS in the case of Appignano and Izmir
- Video summarizing the contents and functionalities

The user can interact with the conceived environment by activating the contents and the modalities (e.g. maps that overlap for showing dynamics of change in sites or the paths of itineraries such as for the pilgrimages). A specific attention has been spent in emphasizing the landscapes.

The user will find a general historical orientation, and some more detailed information about interesting cultural natural heritage sites and experiences in the rural territories. The narratives aim to enhance both tangible and intangible heritage.

The historical information criteria, as mentioned above (see section 2.2.3), have been to stress topics that can be linked to rural regeneration strategies of each Replicator. However, the general aim of this information has been shaping an information about the rural landscape and its dynamics of change. For this purpose, information includes tangible and intangible heritage. Moreover, the developed visual historical narratives provide information about the territory with historical and, where possible, cadastral maps. The visualization tools enable an usage of the historical documentation for understanding the features of the rural areas and their historical main developments.

The Tabula Peutingeriana (Peutinger Table) has been used – where it was historically coherent - as a starting point for visualizing the territories of the Rs. This copy of a Roman map that dates to 1265, made by a monk in Alsace, and 11 sheets of which are now in Nationalbibliothek in Vienna, thus, enables the user a crosscutting basis for visualizing the historical information of the ATLAS about Europe.

The material and information for the development of the narratives, as mentioned above, have been collected by a desk research of cartography, maps, data and pictures and through a new campaign of data specifically addressed to Rs. In some case the active participation of the Replicators also allowed integrating new specific visual information such as the 3D laser scanners (i.e. Negova Castle).

TABLE 9 of Historical CNH Narratives, documentation collected and sources

R	R name	SIA	Regeneration strategy	Historical narrative topics	Sources, data collected/available for historical narrative	Sources
R1	Old traditions and modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg - ARGE - AUSTRIA	Pilgrimage	St Rosalia Cave reactivation	Historical timeline with specification about Hemmaberg archaeological site, Saint Hemma pilgrimage, Hemmaberg archaeological site, the transnational Carinthia Region and its historical political changes, Saint Rosalia Cave, the Tabula Peutingeriana, and territorial developments through historical maps (Carinthia region and Austro-Hungarian empire). Video with an overview of the developed narratives summarization.	Historical cartography, maps, images. Plans, Information about archeological excavations, 3d model extracted by photos and plans.	archaeological pilgrim museum Hammarberg-juanna; Unesco website; Mapio.net; Globasnitz municipality website; Open Street Map; pilgerwege-kaernten website; New York Public Library; Moravian Library; tabula-peutingeriana.de; Google earth Pro; Geopark Karawanke.

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

R2	Magma UNESCO Global Geopark - NORWAY	Food	Geo Food	Farming and territory through historical maps and video visualizing overlapped maps and emphasizing the farming in the maps; geological information about the anorthosite rock; Eigerøy lighthouse and other lighthouses along the coast. 2 videos on the territory and the farming.	Historical cartography on land use (agriculture for food production), geopark municipalities areas governance, photos, conceptual map.	magma geopark website; talknorway website; The Norwegian Lighthouse Society; Norwegian Mapping and Cadastre Authority; Unesco website; Egersund municipality website, google earth pro, Open Street Map; David Rumsey Historical Map collection website.
R3	Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße Odenwald e.V. - GEO-N - GERMANY	Migration	Migrant inclusion through natural landscape enhancing	Lorsch thematic timeline, Lorsch Abbey; the pharmacopeia; Messel Pit timeline, Messel Pit site, the geological site, and the mine, the historical railway. Video.	Pictures, historical maps, plans, conceptual map, manuscript.	UNESCO website; Open Street Map; heritage studies.EU Industrial archeology-communicating world heritage-a task of world heritage convention; Missing Matter website; SWR radio and television broadcaster; Messel museum website; Kloster-Lorsch website; Heidelberg University; Moravian Library; Charles University Central Catalogue.
R4	Kulturno Izobraževalno Drustvo KIBLA KULT PROTUR - SLOVENIA	Art&Festival	Making the Castle a stable cultural centre in the area	Timeline with a thematic development on the Negova castle and first settlement in Negova; Negova Castle architectural changes over time; links with the Negova village and the historical pathways for the castle, the castle as a component of the landscape. A video Video with an overview of the Negoca castle.	Photos, historical iconography, 3D models, 3DLaser Scanner model (point cloud) of external and interior parts of the architectural complex.	UNESCO website; Open Street Map; Google earth pro; Kultprotur website; Youtube (3d video laser scanner model); Researchgate website (Sustainable Conservation of Architectural Heritage. A Case Study of Negova Castle, Slovenia); Jewish heritage website; Europeana; Zavod za varstvo kulturne

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

						dediščine Slovenije (Protection of cultural heritage Regional Units) website.
R5	Comune di Appignano del Tronto (CoApp) - ITALY	Resilience	resilience, community, hub for innovation	Historical maps to visualize the territorial changes starting from the Tabula Peutingeriana, historical political changes of the Italian states territories, the geomorphology of the landscape of the light blue-grey Calanchi (badlands), the earthquake in 2016, and related damages to buildings in the historical city center. Two videos on pre-earthquake and post-earthquake conditions: a video with a simulation of the earthquake and damages to buildings; a second video with a walk within the town historical center with the reconstruction and the new square Piazza Magnitudo 5.5.	Historical pictures, historical maps and view, 3D models, the Tabula Peutingeriana.	Appignano del tronto municipality website; Regione Marche website; Parco dei calanchi e monte ascensione website; google earth pro; INGV terremoti website; tabula-peutingeriana.de website; IGM (Istituto geografico militare).
R6	Integrated Management of Madra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins - TURKEY	Landscape	Arts & Crafts enhancement	Thematic timeline on Izmir; Timeline on Bergama with thematic insights on cultural heritage; Focus on Bergama; the archaeological site of Pergamon; the artisan tradition and handicraft: parchment, basket weaving, music, and carpet weaving, the Bazaar Arasta. A video showing the Bazar through a 3D model and photos contextualizing it.	Maps, photos, 3D models.	Unesco website, Thesis of Michela Baccarin, Research website (A Conservation Approach of Multi-layered Cultural Landscape Areas: The Case Study of Pergamon Red Hall and its Environment); Icomos website; Koç University, Turkey; The Anatolian Kilim and the History of Art Catalog; MDPI Journals (The Sustainability of an Urban Ritual in the Collective Memory: Bergama Kermesi);

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

						<p>Arasta booklet Bergama municipality; Bergama municipality website; Smirne municipality website; Sefa Taskin Archive; Bergama municipality Archive.</p>
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5.4.1 R1 Old traditions and modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg

The Geopark Karavanke includes a transnational area with total of 14 municipalities: from Austria (9) and Slovenia (5) that are Zell/Sele, Gallizien, Eisenkappel/Telezna Kapla, Sittersdorf, Globasnitz/Globasnica, Feistritz ob Bleiburg/Bistrica nad Pliberkom, Bleiburg/Pliberk, Neuhaus, Lavamünd, Črna na Koroškem, Mežica, Prevalje, Ravne na Koroškem and Dravograd). The Geopark Karavanke extends between two 2,000-metre-high Alpine peaks: the Petzen/Mt. Peca and the Koschuta Massif. It is characterized by rich geological diversity between the Alps and the Dinarides. The topographic map allows to have an idea of the mountain chain which is connecting and at the same time dividing the regions on both sides of the border of Slovenia and Austria.

For the development of the baseline of RURITAGE project, only 1 municipality (Globasnitz/Globasnica) has been considered, because is where the main Pilgrimage place is located. However, the developed historical narratives aim at providing a wider context of understanding for the area. They show the region of Carinthia as a transnational region by explaining the historical political changes and the plebiscite that created the separation of the region between the two countries. Moreover, they also allow understanding the pilgrimage of Saint Hemma as the path of a bigger itinerary across regions, and finally focus on the Cave of Saint Rosalia for explaining the significance of the worship place.

The historical timeline includes specifications about Hemmaberg archaeological site.

The visualization of the territory in the map shows the Tabula Peutingeriana and territorial developments of Carinthia region and Austro-Hungarian empire. Visual narratives also aim to increase the understanding of the archaeological site of Hemmaberg. A video enables an overview of the developed narratives summarization.

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas
Route to Hemmaberg

Figure 27 R1 Pilgrimage Route to Hemmaberg

the initiative of the diocesan bishop of Carinthia, Dr. Alois Schwarz, in collaboration with the regional development department of Central Carinthia with the Carinthian Catholic Church, with the regional cooperation of the Lower Carinthia and with partners from Styria and Slovenia.

HEMMA PILGRIMAGE

GEOREFERENCING IN GOOGLE EARTH

HISTORICAL MAPS

DESCRIPTION OF THE PATH

A total of eight paths lead to Gurk. They start in Sveta Ana and Irna na Koroškem in Slovenia, Admont and St. Hemma near Edelschrott in Styria and in Millstatt, Ossiach, Turrach and Karnburg in Carinthia. The different routes have a variable length and difficulty and allow the pilgrim to choose to start a lighter variant or, if the weather is sufficient, to be on the road for a week.

Figure 28 Saint Hemma Pilgrimage path

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

BACK

CARINTHIA

Transformation of national borders and Carinthia over the years.

Borders 1914.

< 4-7 >

Figure 29 Carinthia po

Figure 39 Historical Timeline

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

5.4.2 R2 Magma UNESCO Global Geopark

Magma UNESCO Global Geopark is situated in southwest Norway covering 5 municipalities (Eigersund, Sokndal, Lund and Bjerkreim in Rogaland County and Flekkefjord in Vest-Agder County) and parts of two regions (Rogaland County and Vest-Agder County). The four municipalities in Rogaland County also comprise the Dalane district, comprising a total administrative area of 2.329 km².

UNESCO has defined its main specificity as an area of “unique magmatic geology”. The history of this territory goes back up 1.5 billion years. Through millions of years from red-hot magma, mountains and glaciers, geological processes developed several changes till the current landscape. The landscape is characterized by magmatic rocks around 930-920 million years old. This rock type is called anorthosite. It is quite unusual in the Earth while it is more common in the moon.

The developed historical CNH narratives include a timeline that visualizes an history beginning as early as 1.5 billion years ago when red-hot magma and sky-high mountains characterized the region’s magmatic geology. A specific focus is on the historical representation of the territory through the possibility to visualize historical and cadastral maps. The visualization tools show the area by emphasizing the main attributes of the landscape. An historical focus is also provided on the Eigerøy Lighthouse (1854), that is the oldest cast iron lighthouse in Norway.

THE HISTORICAL CADASTRE: THE CITY OF EIGERSUND

Eigersund is a municipality in the county of Rogaland. The territory on which the city stands appears to have been inhabited since prehistoric times and numerous remains of human settlements dating back to the 6th century AD. have been found in the city.

1857

1868

1896

1914

DOWNLOAD

1857

1868

Figure 40

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

Eigerøy Lighthouse History

From 1843 to 1851 there were four serious shipwrecks outside Egersund with a total of 40 fatalities. The lighthouse was therefore built to show the rent way into the city, but also to give land recognition in a good way. In order to achieve the latter, it was important that the lighthouse was high, and it was therefore for the first time in Norway built a cast iron tower of plates that were screwed together on the construction site. However, the lighthouse was unsure if this would be solid enough and fed the entire tower inside with 70,000 bricks. At the top there was a lamphouse with a 1st order heating apparatus that showed solid white light. In 1897, the light was reinforced with a lightning flasher. In 1934, eigerøy lighthouse was electrified and received a diafon fog signal. This was Norway's first cast iron lighthouse, and its success has encouraged the construction of many more on the Norwegian coast.

The picture is taken from the National Archives. Egerøy, Eigersund Archive institution, The National Archives Archive name: Fyrdirektoratet Place: Norway, Rogaland, Eigersund, Date : between 1890 and 1900

Figure 41

5.4.3 R3 Geo-Naturpark Bergstraße Odenwald e.V. - GEO-N

The Geopark territory is located in the Southwest of Germany between the rivers Rhine (W), Main (N) and Neckar (S), and the Odenwald hills in the centre. It encompasses 9 counties and 105 municipalities, including the University cities of Darmstadt and Heidelberg. The Geopark boundaries are represented by the territorial boundaries of the counties and municipalities, which includes regions in the states of Hesse, Bavaria and Baden-Württemberg. The area includes three UNESCO World Heritage Sites that are Messel Pit, Lorsch Abbey and Altenmüster of Lorsch, Roman Limes. In the area there is a European Nature Reserve for birds. The land use mostly includes agriculture in Rhine valley, farming in Crystalline Odenwald, and forestry in Bunter Sandstone Odenwald. The site also includes an item registered by the UNESCO in the Memory of the World Register: the Lorsch Pharmacopoeia in the Bamberg State Library.

The historical CNH focus on the UNESCO sites Messel Pit Fossil Site and Lorsch Abbey by providing some insights. The abbey is shown through historical iconography that emphasizes its representation in the landscape. The Lorsch religious complex (since 764) is located in the Hesse town. According to the declaration of its outstanding value the architectural remain is "one of the very rare buildings from the Carolingian era whose original appearance is intact". The overlapping between historical iconography and recent photos is also used for visualizing the changes of the landscape context of the Torhall (i.e. the monumental entrance) and its perception. Links to the UNESCO website provide to access more information and medias.

According to UNESCO definition, the Messel Pit in the Land of Hesse is the richest site in the world for understanding the living environment of the Eocene, between 57 million and 36 million years ago, when mammals became firmly established in all principal land ecosystems. Although the site has been the former site of an oil shale mine, extraordinary fossils have been preserved which allows for the reconstruction of the morphology of fauna and flora as well as that of their environment. The visual narrative shows simulations of the Messel Pit movements through time. Some information and photos are also provided on the matter of the mine, the activity of which has been discontinued in the late 1960's.

An historical narrative also provides information about the Intangible Heritage of The Lorsch Pharmacopoeia (Msc.Med.1) in the Bamberg State Library is the earliest, reliably datable compendium of classical remedies in the Greco-Roman tradition from the (Latin) Early Middle Ages in Europe.

BACK

LORSCH ABBEY

Lorsch Abbey on a colored copper engraving by Matthäus Merian, around 1615.
An engraving by Matthäus Merian from 1615 showing what Lorsch Abbey was supposed to look like in the early 17th century.

LORSCH ABBEY - PLAN

Figure 42

Figure 42 Lorsch Abbey Timeline

< 2-7 >

Figure 43 Map of the Metzel Pit

5.4.4 R4 Kulturno izobrazevalno Drustvo KIBLA

The area includes the village of Negova in the hills in the west part of the municipality of Gornja Radgona, which is located at the north eastern part of Slovenia namely at the area of Ščavnica valley and at the wine-growing area of the Radgona hills. It borders neighbouring Austria along the Mura River and on the other borders with municipalities of Apače, Radenci, Sveti Jurij ob Ščavnici, Cerkevnik, Benedikt, Sveta Ana in Sveta Trojica v Slovenskih goricah. It measures 75 km² and is part of the Pomurska statistical region. The municipality of Gornja Radgona covers 30 settlements, where, according to the available data for 2016, a total of 8,471 persons live. The mean age of people in Gornja Radgona is 44 years, which is higher than the national average (42.6). The municipality is known for fairs, viticulture and Gornja Radgona sparkling wine. The main historical building is the Negova Castle.

The historical CNH narratives focus on the Negova Castle as a component of the territory and the landscape. The Castle is a monument registered as national importance. Several changes in its ownership and function through centuries and a fire in the 20th Century have caused many modifications till the present condition. The historical iconography, pathways and the architectural complex composition suggest that in the past there was a stronger connection with the village, while the enlargements and a new entrance have changed the perception of the castle in the landscape. An architectural study for the historical conservation of the Castle have been recently published (Nataša Jurgec Gurnick, Ljubo Lah, 'Sustainable Conservation of Architectural Heritage. A Case Study of Negova Castle', Slovenia, *International Journal on Proceedings of Science and Technology*, 2019, DOI: 10.21625/resourceedings.v2i2.603). The Replicator has produced a 3DLaser scanner for the RURITAGE Atlas.

Negova castle - Original entrance (yellow route)

Entry routes: the original entrance to the old castle in yellow; in red the entrance today. Over time the village developed in the southern part of the hill, changing the access route.

J. F. Kaiser - lithographed views of the towns, markets and castles of Steyermark, Graz, 1824-1833.

Figure 44 Interactive visualization of the historical iconography by emphasizing the landscape view

BACK

NEGOVA VILLAGE

Figure 45 The Negova castle 3D model contextualized with the village and the rural area

Click on the black dot to open the link

Figure 46 R4 Timeline with insights on Negova Castle

5.4.5 R5 Comune di Appignano del Tronto (CoApp)

Appignano Del Tronto is located in the south of Marche Region (among central regions of Italy) in the Tronto River basin, at an altitude of about 194 m a.s.l-the territory is between 90 and 400 m. In a territory mostly hilly, Appignano del Tronto is characterized by the presence of dip slope rolling hills and light blue anti-dip slope rocky badlands. This natural landscape has been shaped by three torrential rivers, “Chifente”, “Pioppo” and “Volubile”, which create a beautiful natural landscape. They also represent the hydrogeological fragility of this area.

This territory has a traditional rural vocation with farming (cereals and grapes, high quality olive oils, PDO olives, organic vegetable and fruit) and sheep farming (ovine, bovine and caprine animals), agricultural businesses (various mills, dairies, wine cellars, organic and typical bakeries) and craft firms (manufacturing industries producing ceramic, laces, bobbins, embroidered jewels, etc.). The earthquakes in 2016 have caused many damages to buildings and to social and economic condition. The trend towards depopulation has been intensified due to earthquakes in 2016 and 2017.

The Historical CNH narratives allow visualizing the territorial changes starting from the Tabula Peutingeriana. Schematic drawings shape historical political changes of the territory in the context of the Italian states before the 19th century unification of the country. Maps and photos also highlight the landscapes geo-morphology with the light blue-grey badlands. the earthquake in 2016 and related damages to buildings in the historical city centre. Two videos on pre-earthquake and post-earthquake conditions: a video with a simulation of the earthquake and damages to buildings; a second video with a walk within the town historical centre with the reconstruction and the new square Piazza Magnitudo 5.5.

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

Appignano del Tronto -
React after a disaster

- Timeline
- Historical maps
- Earthquake
- Badlands

Figure 47 the homepage of Appignano del Tronto

HISTORICAL MAPS

DOWNLOAD

1600

1757

1894

cadastre

- 1600
- 1757
- 1894
- cadastre

"Pianta Antica" di Ascoli, Attributed to Ferdinando Fabiani, XVII century

1 di 3 selezionati, 278,84 GB disponibili

Figure 48 Historical maps of Appignano

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

washout on degraded clayey rocks, with scarce vegetation cover and therefore not very protected from runoff. It is (more simply) the deep furrows in the ground along the side of a mountain or a hill. Therefore the landscape of the badlands is constantly changing. These formations are located in Castignano, Appignano del Tronto, Ripatransone and Ascoli Piceno on the eastern side of the Brettia stream where they develop for about 5 km with southern exposure, and on the eastern side of the Chifenti stream where they extend for about 3

View of the Badlands and Mount Ascensione

6.30 am

12.30 am

6.30 pm

Figure 49 The badlands

TABULA PEUTINGERIANA

Tabula Peutingeriana is a 12th-13th century copy of an ancient roman map showing the military routes of the Roman Empire, called *cursus publicus*. The map in 2007 it was included by UNESCO in the World Memory Register.

Roma

Ascoli Piceno

1
2

Tabula Peutingeriana

Figure 50 Appignano in the Tabula Peutingeriana

**3D SIMULATION OF THE HISTORICAL CENTER OF
APPIGNANO DEL TRONTO**

Figure 51 Screenshot of the video of 2016 earthquake simulation in Appignano

5.4.6 R6 Izmir Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins

The area of the Izmir Replicator includes Bergama, Dikili and Kinik district municipalities. The region is located on the Bakircay Basin of Izmir. This fertile agricultural basin has been home historically to many ancient civilizations including the world-famous historical heritage site of Pergamon. The area for the proposed Geopark covers Bergama, Dikili and Foça district municipalities. The main source of income is agriculture. The region's agricultural products of particular fame are, for instance, the grapes and the pine nuts from the highlands of Kozak, but the region is also an olive producing area, one of the main agricultural outputs. The area of influence of the Izmir Metropolitan Area has been gradually extended by laws of urbanism. According to projections, in 2030 it is estimated that Izmir metropolitan area will be 6.2 million, and in 2050 the population will rise to 8 million and almost double in a 30 years period.

The focus of the historical information about this wide and diverse area is mostly Bergama and Izmir. The Atlas provides a timeline on Izmir and a timeline on Bergama with thematic insights on cultural heritage. The visual narratives about Bergama include the relations between Bergama and the archaeological site of Pergamon; the artisan tradition and handicraft of parchment, basket weaving, music instruments and carpet weaving and the Bergama districts. A reconstruction with a 3D model of Bazaar Arasta connects spatial data with these intangible values.

D1.3 RURITAGE Atlas

Bergama, Atmaca Neighbourhood, basket weaving

Figure 52 Handcraft of basket weaving in Bergama and Atmaca district

Slideshow of Historic photos of Arasta Bazaar

Figure 53 The Arasta Bazar in a historical photo

**The Turkish Carpets and the role of
the Women**

Figure 54 Carpets crat in the region traditions.

Conclusion and next steps

The Atlas with its developed, stored, organized and visualized information is made available at the URL: www.ruritage-ecosystem.eu/atlas at M.13 for RMs and Rs interaction according to the RURITAGE methodology and challenges. It is also under continuous updating complementary to the RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem development for exploiting data by generating more narratives and more effective inquiries. The final graphical interface and more refined functional developments related to the overall RURITAGE challenges implementation will be developed in Task 5.1 to made available with the D.5.3 at M36.

The “creative mapping” of Task 1.3 was systematically developed:

- **methodologically** by data gathering through the End-users participation
- **technologically** by combining WEB GIS with digital platform performances in visualisation and data management
- **in the visualisation**, by developing an interface with visual narratives and inquiries through the digital platform functions.
-

This output allows an innovative Atlas for Heritage-le Rural Regeneration Strategies. It contributes to reflect on the cultural natural heritage potential and to refine the landscape mapping conceptual and technological practices with its specifications addressing RURITAGE challenges.

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Annex I: Summer and Winter Campaigns Questionnaires

Annex II: List of attributes for QGIS

Annex III: Description of 3D modelling process

Annex IV: Copyright Licence

ANNEX I: Summer and Winter Campaigns Questionnaires

We aim to map a long-term and a short-term dynamic of change. The long term will cover back about 100 years or more (depending by the different cadastres). The short term will be defined as post WWII and possibly according to the specificity of each CNL Cultural Natural Landscapes and related RMs.

Common template to be filled for each data

How to collect data

QUESTIONS to all RMs

To be filled from all Role Models.

Please find 8 questions templates to fill.

Each template has a **Glossary** referred to it and situated at its right.

For the questions in which you are asked to produce a map, please provide us the file .jpg 600 dpi, denominated as follow: nameofthe RM_no.question_map (e.g. POLITO_Q7_map).

PILGRIMAGE/ RURAL FOOD/MIGRATION/ART_FESTIVAL/RESILIENCE/LANDSCAPE

To be filled by RM related to each specific SIA.

Each template has a Glossary referred to it and situated at its right.

For the questions in which you are asked to produce a map, please provide us the file .jpg 600 dpi, denominated as follow: nameofthe RM_no.question_map (e.g. RM_Q7_map)

In case of doubt, please don't hesitate to contact us!!!!

ruritage@polito.it

RURITAGE

RM's WINTER MAPPING CAMPAIGN

The second stage of questionnaire aims to complete the first mapping campaign and collect more information about the interaction between people and cultural natural landscapes (CNL). If you didn't already send us first Campaign requested information, please, provide now. The questions you will answer will help us to map how people interact with CNL, illustrate the SIA. Therefore, we kindly ask you to keep in mind this specific focus answering questions.

*You are kindly **asked to upload** scans (or other useful reproduction or accessible link) of relevant historical and recent visual (e.g. photographs, engravings, videos, architectural drawings, maps, etc.), audio (e.g. videos, interviews,), and textual material (e.g. documents, travel literature, and other relevant literary descriptions, etc.), or information about objects (e.g. coins, archaeological remains, etc.). If you can't directly add these kind of media on the map you can just send it as zip files but please remember to insert the name of the file inside the additional information.*

When a question is not clear, please do not hesitate to contact us through ruritage@polito.it.

1. The SIA area

Q1a: Please, **draw on the map the perimeter of SIA** (Systemic Innovation Area)

In particular

Q1a for R1 pilgrimage: draw the pilgrimage route and the area of its influence.

Q1a for R2 sustainable local food production: draw the area of production.

Q1a for R3 migration: draw the area of buildings for migration hospitality and related activity.

Q1a for R4 art and festivals; draw the locations area.

Q1a for R5 resilience; draw the areas that were affected from a damage or under the risk of natural disasters. In case that there were preventive trainings or monitor activities, please indicate the location.

Q1a for R6 integrated landscape management; please **draw** the system of CNH assets (vineyards, agricultural production, dams, etc.)

Q1b: Please select the level of interaction of your CNL with other additional SIAs. Please give a value in a hierarchical order (1 is your SIA, 7 is the least interaction)

- a) Pilgrimage
- b) Sustainable Local Food Production
- c) Migration
- d) Art and festivals
- e) Resilience
- f) Integrated Landscape Management

Q1c: Please **map** more areas that are relevant as area of influence of your SIA, as related to the specific mentioned aspects. Use different layers to differentiate also according to selected numbered areas (1B).

In particular,

For a) Pilgrimage:

draw in the map the pilgrimage routes in your SIA, the sites, and the area of its influence;

point any relevant related (historical and recent) buildings. Use different layers to indicate different ancient routes (variations of the recent ones).

Fill in here

Name of the Pilgrimage:

Name of the devotion sites:

If existing, indicate special dates:

Please indicate here some more information (beginnings, itinerary, historical buildings, traditions):

.....

.....

List the buildings for hospitality and other related activity

1.....

2.....

For b) Sustainable local food production:

draw the major area of production and indicate the major products.

Fill in here

Major Products:

Historical productions:

New introduced productions:

For c) Migration:

point on the buildings for migration hospitality and related activity

Fill in here

Functions of the building

Rehabilitation of historical buildings

For d) Art and festivals;

draw the locations.

Fill in here

Name of the Art and Festival

Dates/season

For e) Resilience;

draw the areas that were eventually affected from a damage or under the risk of natural disasters. In case that there were preventive trainings and monitoring, please indicate the location of these activities.

Fill in here

Past natural disaster

Year

For f) Integrated landscape management; please

draw the most significant elements of elements of system of CNH

Fill in here

Elements description:

Elements integration:

Please upload relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.). For each material indicate a number to be filled in here with related information

1. Description
2. Eventually Authors, Title, Date and the preservation site or from where it has been extracted
3. Eventual link to the source

Q1d: Indicate some relevant changes in your SIA in past/recent times and provide information (e.g. new water channel, new tunnel, new dam, new kind of production, etc.)

Please **map** the areas and indicate a temporal frame.

1. Area description
Temporal frame
Information about the changes

2....

Please upload relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.). For each material indicate a number to be filled in here with related information

1. Description
2. Author, Title, Date and source or from where it has been extracted
3. Eventual link to the source
- 4.

Q1e: Are there any characterization of the areas within your SIA? If yes, please, **draw** the areas in the map.

- a) Natural area
- b) Rural area
- c) Unpopulated area
- d) Historic urban center
- e) Area of gentrification
- f) Area of old industrialization
- g) Area of recent industrialization
- h) Area under the risk of natural disasters
- i) Other. Please Specify

Q1f: Related with your SIA: Is there an inventory of the heritage sites/buildings of your area?

- a) Yes. (Please provide a link or indicate the institution which beholds the inventory).
- b) No-

2. Land Uses

Question 2a: Please indicate your most recent cadaster

- Description
- Date
- Link if accessible

Please upload digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else) related to your SIA (or send us appropriate accessible links).
Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

Q 2b: Please indicate other ancient geometrical parcel cadasters of which you provide digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else).

Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

Description

Date

Please upload digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else) related to your SIA (or send us appropriate accessible links).

Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

Q 2c: Please provide digitised reproductions of maps of the area after WWII by indicating eventual damages and state of the site.

Description

Date

Use this field if you like provide more information:

Upload (photograph, engraving, maps scans). For each map indicate a number to be filled in with related information

Q 2d: Please provide digitised reproductions of historical maps of the area.

Description

Date

Use this field if you like provide more information

Upload (photograph, engraving, maps scans). For each map indicate a number to be filled in with related information

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information:

2. Description (Author, Title, Date)

More information:

3.

Q 2e: Please indicate the recent situation regarding prevalent land uses in your area. If possible provide **thematic maps** with uses descriptions

Indicate if

- a) The essential activity and identifies the largest surface within the region (more than 50%).

Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation:

The harvesting period

- b) Indicate if the Agriculture is relevant among other activities (30%-50%)

- a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation

The harvesting period

- c) Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation:

- a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation

The harvesting period

- d) Agriculture is limited (less than 30%).
 - a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation
The harvesting period
- e) No agricultural activity

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.) also related to different kind of productions.

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q 2f: Please indicate if there are any crafts productions, and if especially related with local traditions.

Description of crafts productions

If yes, please, draw the boundaries of area of craft production or point the individual buildings.

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Question 2g: Please indicate if there is any other major activity or point the individual buildings

Description

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

3. Sites

Q 3a: Are there any UNESCO World Heritage Sites in your area?

If yes, please **draw the boundaries of area** on the map (or **point** the individual buildings if serial site).

Name

Original period (e.g. 15th Century)

Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q 3b: Are there any other listed (national, local) sites? If yes, please indicate the inscription year, draw the boundaries of area (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Name
Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q 3c: Are there any other historic sites that could be relevant for local history and traditions? If yes, please, draw the boundaries of area (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Name
Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q 3d : Are there any historic/traditional itineraries?
If yes, please, **draw the** itinerary and **point** individual related elements/buildings.

Name
Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q3e: Are there any sites that are/has become specifically popular?
If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area and specify.

- a) Illustrated in literature (novels, poems)
- b) Popular for traditional storytelling
- c) Popular because of recent movie/TV show
- d) Especially Popular in tourist guides

e) other

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

4. Open air activities

Q4a: Are there any relevant sites for periodic festivals?

If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area on the map and **point** if there are individual buildings to be related to the festivals.

Please list the festivals, indicate if related to traditional festivities, indicate the dates or the period of the year, and draw (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

- a) art festival
- b) food festival
- c) religious
- d) other cultural thematic festival (Specify:.....)

Name of the festival

Dates if established

Period of the year

Use this field if you like to provide more information.....

Name of the festivals

.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q4b: Are there any recurrent/seasonal open-air specific (cultural/traditional) activities?

If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area, and the dates/periods.

- a) agenda of cultural events
- b) theater agenda
- c) recurring exhibitions
- d) crafts fair
- e) parades
- f) religious festivities
- g) other. Specify

Name of the recurrent activity

Dates if established
Period of the year
Use this field if you like provide more information.....
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).
Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q4c: Are there any other open-air periodical activities?
If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area of

- a) Daily food market
- b) Periodic food market
- c) Periodic any staff/goods market
- d) Periodic traditional market
- e) Periodic antiquities market
- f) Fairs
- g) Other (specify)

Indicate:
Name of the recurrent activity
Dates if established
Period of the year
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).
Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q4d: Please indicate if in your area there was/has been planned any extraordinary event and if possible draw/point the interest area in the map (e.g. stage of races, expo, etc.)

Indicate:
Name of the extraordinary event
Occurred
Planned and scheduled
Conceived to be planned
Dates/year
Period of the year
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

5. HISTORIC BUILDINGS AND MONUMENTS

Q5a: Are there any UNESCO World Heritage buildings in your area?

If yes, please **point** the individual buildings.

Name
Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q5b: Are there any other listed (national, local) buildings/monuments?

If yes, please **point** individual buildings/monuments. Indicate

Name
Date or period of the building/monuments
Description
Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q5c: Are there any other historic buildings that could be relevant for local history and traditions?

If yes, please, **point** the individual buildings. Indicate

Name
Date or period of the building/monuments
Description
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information

Q5d: Are there any relevant rehabilitated historic buildings that have been devoted to new relevant public/collective activities?

If yes, please, **point** the buildings.

- a) for cultural activities
- b) for activities related to art and festivals
- c) for migrants hospitality
- d) for public authority
- e) for tourism
- f) there aren't rehabilitated historic buildings for public uses
- g) other

Name
 Date of the building/monuments
 Description
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Q5e: Are there any relevant old/historic farms? If yes, please, point on the map.

Name
 Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Q5f: Are there any relevant recent building that have been built? If yes, please, point on the map and indicate:

- a) cultural activities
- b) production
- c) sustainable energy production
- d) trade hub
- e) other. Specify

Name
 Function
 Year of construction
 10 to 5 years

5 to 1 years
less than 1 year

Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q5.g Are there any other relevant sites /buildings in your SIA?
Please point/draw in the map and indicate

Name
Function
Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q5.h According to the cultural heritage buildings that you have pointed and listed, please provide more specific documentation available. In particular, provide or indicate where it is available:
Name the building:

- a) architectural drawing
 - a. author
 - b. date
- b) 3D model
 - a. author
 - b. date
- c) photograph
 - a. author
 - b. date
- d) video
 - a. author
 - b. date
- e) other

6. The relation of your area to the closest urban area

Question 6a: Please indicate the closest and the most related urban area and **draw/point** in the map.

- a) No relevant relation, our area is self-sufficient.
- b) Limited relation, only for bureaucratic processes and governance actions.
- c) Intermediate relation, residences go to urban areas for major needs such as hospitals, municipal registrations, etc.
- d) Strong relation, majority of residences go to urban areas on a daily basis.

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Question 6b: Please indicate and **point** in the map the cultural organisations and buildings within the SIA area and/or the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) Preservation cultural heritage institutions
- b) Museums
- c) Ecomuseums
- d) Theaters
- e) Libraries
- f) Art galleries
- g) Public Archives
- h) Cinemas
- i) Archaeological sites
- j) Other. Specify

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Q6c: Please indicate and **point** in the map important education buildings within the SIA area and/or indicate the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) primary schools
- b) high schools
- c) universities
- d) special training programs (specify)

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Q6d: Please indicate and **point** in the map, relevant buildings of local authority and public services within the SIA area or indicate the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) local authority
- b) regional authority
- c) hospital
- d) health clinic
- e) emergency room
- f) general market
- g) specialised market

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6e: Indicate **draw or point** in the map the access to your area and the relation of your area to the closest urban area and beyond through the most relevant infrastructures.

Use different layers or colors to differentiate the major from the minor infrastructure.

- a) highways (please draw a line)
- b) national streets (please draw a line)
- c) regional street ((please draw a line)
- d) local street relevant for the access to the SIA (please draw a line)
- e) bridges
- f) airports
- g) railway (please draw a line)
 - a. Specify major direct connections
- h) railway stations
 - a. high speed train stops
- i) bus stations (long-distance)

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6f: Are there more planned/ongoing infrastructures that can be important in linking the area within the region and/or beyond? Please indicate and **draw** in the map:

- a) airport
- b) railway
- c) street
- d) bridge
- e) travel hub

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6g: Are/were there any historical infrastructures crucial in linking the area within the region and/or beyond? Please show on the map.

- a) street
- b) bridge
- c) railway
- d) other

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6h: Please indicate if in the closest urban area there has/has been planned any extraordinary event and if possible point the interest area in the map

Indicate:

Name of the extraordinary event

Planned and scheduled

Conceived to be planned

Dates/year

Period of the year

Use this field if you like provide more information

7. Tourism

Question 7a: Please **draw/point** in the map, important tourist information offices within your area. Please upload visual material (photograph, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Question 7b: Please indicate if there are descriptions panels for sites/buildings of cultural interest that you've listed. Please when possible **point** in the map or specify.

Indicate if there are links to digital resources like QR code

Use this field for providing information

Please upload visual material for cultural signs (photograph, video, drawings, map, etc.)

Question 7c: Please indicate if there have been/are any old or ongoing tourist communication campaign and **draw/point** in the map if has interested specific sites/building

Name of the site/building

Year of the tourist campaign

Use this field for providing information

Please upload visual material for relevant advertising (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.)

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

8. Multimedia and Digital Tools

For the following data, please draw or point in the map if the information is coherent. If not possible, fill in the answers without point and attached the materials you can provide.

Q8a: Are there any kind of mapping and digital products/resources/tools related with your SIA?

- a) GIS
- b) 3D model
- c) Mobile APPs
- d) video
- e) other. Specify

Please provide the link and/or information about the creator

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Link

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Upload any visual materials

Q8b: Are there any kind of movies or advertising that have used the SIA as scenario? Have been produced some specific videos for your areas?

- a) Cinema
- b) television and information channels
- c) tourism
- d) advertising
- e) historic reconstruction in museum
- f) special events
- g) other. Specify

Please provide information

Description (Title, creator, date)

Media

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Please provide visual material

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Media

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Question 8c: Have any audio materials been produced? Could you provide information and eventually materials? Have they been produced for

- a) cultural projects
- b) interviews
- c) educational projects
- d) other. Specify

*The questionnaire aims to collect information for mapping and visualizing each SIA (Systemic Innovation Area) area in RURITAGE ATLAS. Data and images aim to localize and visualise the rich variety of sites, the interactions between communities and cultural natural landscapes (CNL), the network of elements, and the specific characters (i.e. cultural, natural, topographical, historical, architectural). The questions you will answer will help illustrate tangible and intangible heritage and other peculiarities, understand how people interact with CNL, what kind of change occurs at which level as an outcome of this interaction, and the SIA potentialities. Therefore, we kindly ask you to keep in mind this specific focus answering questions. You are kindly **asked to upload** scans (or other useful reproduction or accessible link) of relevant historical and recent visual (e.g. photographs, engravings, videos, architectural drawings, maps, etc.), audio (e.g. videos, interviews,), and textual material (e.g. documents, travel literature, and other relevant literary descriptions, etc.), or information about objects (e.g. coins, archaeological remains, etc.). If you can't directly add these kind of media on the map you can just send it as zip files but please remember to insert the name of the file inside the additional information.*

When a question is not clear, please do not hesitate to contact us through ruritage@polito.it.

1. The SIA area

Q1a: Please, **draw on the map the perimeter of SIA** (Systemic Innovation Area)

In particular

Q1a for R1 pilgrimage: draw the pilgrimage route and the area of its influence.

Q1a for R2 sustainable local food production: draw the area of production.

Q1a for R3 migration: draw the area of buildings for migration hospitality and related activity.

Q1a for R4 art and festivals; draw the locations area.

Q1a for R5 resilience; draw the areas that were affected from a damage or under the risk of natural disasters. In case that there were preventive trainings or monitor activities, please indicate the location.

Q1a for R6 integrated landscape management; please **draw** the system of CNH assets (vineyards, agricultural production, dams, etc.)

Q1b: Please select the level of interaction of your CNL with other additional SIAs. Please give a value in a hierarchical order (1 is your SIA, 7 is the least interaction)

- a) Pilgrimage
- b) Sustainable Local Food Production
- c) Migration
- d) Art and festivals
- e) Resilience
- f) Integrated Landscape Management

Q1c: Please map more areas that are relevant as area of influence of your SIA, as related to the specific mentioned aspects. Use different layers to differentiate also according to selected numbered areas (1B).

In particular,

For a) Pilgrimage:

draw in the map if there are the pilgrimage routes, the sites, and the area of its influence; **point** any relevant related (historical and recent) buildings. Use different entries to indicate different ancient routes (variations of the recent ones).

Fill in here

Name of the Pilgrimage:

Name of the devotion site:

If existing, indicate special dates:

Please indicate here some more information (beginnings, itinerary, historical buildings, traditions):

.....
.....

List the buildings for hospitality and other related activity

- 1.....
- 2.....

Written documents

- 1.(e.g.traveller' ancient description)...
-

Visual documentation

- 1.(e.g.ancient itinerary...).....

Objects

- 1. (e.g. Devotion object...).....

For b) Sustainable local food production:

draw the major area of production and indicate the major products.

Fill in here

Major Products:

Historical productions:

New introduced productions:

For c) Migration:

point on the buildings for migration hospitality and related activity

Fill in here

Functions of the building

Rehabilitation of historical buildings

For d) Art and festivals;

draw the locations.

Fill in here

Name of the Art and Festival
Dates/season

For e) Resilience;

draw the areas that were eventually affected from a damage or under the risk of natural disasters. In case that there were preventive trainings and monitoring, please indicate the location of these activities.

Fill in here

Past natural disaster

Year

For f) Integrated landscape management; please

draw the most significant elements of elements of system of CNH

Fill in here

Elements description:

Elements integration:

Please upload relevant historical and recent visual, written and audio materials. For each material indicate a number to be filled in here with related information

1. Description

Eventually Authors, Title, Date and the preservation site or from where it has been extracted

Eventual link to the source

Q1d: Indicate some relevant changes in your SIA in past/recent times and provide information (e.g. new water channel, new tunnel, new dam, new kind of production, etc.)

Please **map** the areas and indicate a temporal frame.

1. Area description

Temporal frame

Information about the changes

2....

Please upload relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.). For each material indicate a number to be filled in here with related information

1. Description

2. Author, Title, Date and source or from where it has been extracted

3. Eventual link to the source

4.

Q1e: Are there any characterization of the areas within your SIA? If yes, please, **draw** the areas in the map.

a) Natural area

b) Rural area

c) Unpopulated area

d) Historic urban center

- e) Area of gentrification
- f) Area of old industrialization
- g) Area of recent industrialization
- h) Area under the risk of natural disasters
- i) Other. Please Specify

Q1f: Related with your SIA: Is there an inventory of the heritage sites/buildings of your area?

- a) Yes. (Please provide a link or indicate the institution which beholds the inventory).
- b) No-

2. Land Uses

Question 2a: Please indicate your most recent cadaster

- Description
- Date
- Link if accessible

Please upload digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else) related to your SIA (or send us appropriate accessible links).

Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

Q 2b: Please indicate other ancient geometrical parcel cadasters of which you provide digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else).

Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

- Description
- Date

Please upload digitised reproductions (and associated cadastral data about uses or else) related to your SIA (or send us appropriate accessible links).

Please provide with colour scans a 300 dpi TIFF.

Q 2c: Please provide digitised reproductions of maps of the area before and after WWII by indicating eventual damages and state of the site.

- Description
- Date

Use this field if you like provide more information:

Upload (photograph, engraving, maps scans). For each map indicate a number to be filled in with related information

Q 2d: Please provide digitised reproductions of historical maps of the area.

- Description
- Date

Use this field if you like provide more information

Upload (photograph, engraving, maps scans). For each map indicate a number to be filled in with related information

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information:

2. Description (Author, Title, Date)

More information:

3.

Q 2e: Please indicate the recent situation regarding prevalent land uses in your area. If possible provide **thematic maps** with uses descriptions

Indicate if

- a) The essential activity and identifies the largest surface within the region (more than 50%).

Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation:

The harvesting period

- b) Indicate if the Agriculture is relevant among other activities (30%-50%)

- a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation

The harvesting period

- c) Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation:

- a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation

The harvesting period

- d) Agriculture is limited (less than 30%).

- a. Indicate if there are any prevalent cultivation

The harvesting period

- e) No agricultural activity

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.) also related to different kind of productions.

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q 2f: Please indicate if there are any crafts productions, and if especially related with local traditions.

Description of crafts productions

If yes, please, draw the boundaries of area of craft production or point the individual buildings.

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Question 2g: Please indicate if there is any other major activity or point the individual buildings

Description

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

3. Sites

Q 3a: Are there any UNESCO World Heritage Sites in your area?

If yes, please **draw the boundaries of area** on the map (or **point** the individual buildings if serial site).

Name

Original period (e.g. 15th Century)

Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q 3b: Are there any other listed (national, local) sites? If yes, please indicate the inscription year, draw the boundaries of area (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Name

Original period (e.g. 15th Century)

Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q 3c: Are there any other historic sites that could be relevant for local history and traditions? If yes, please, draw the boundaries of area (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Name

Original period (e.g. 15th Century)

Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q 3d : Are there any historic/traditional itineraries?

If yes, please, **draw the** itinerary and **point** individual related elements/buildings.

Name
Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

1. Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

Q3e: Are there any sites that are/has become specifically popular?

If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area and specify.

a) Illustrated in literature (novels, poems).

Please specify:

b) Popular for traditional storytelling.

Please specify

c) Popular because of recent movie/TV show

Please specify

d) Especially Popular in tourist guides

Please specify

e) Other. Please specify

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
...

4. Open air activities

Q4a: Are there any relevant sites for periodic festivals?

If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area on the map and **point** if there are individual buildings to be related to the festivals.

Please list the festivals, indicate if related to traditional festivities, indicate the dates or the period of the year, and draw (or indicate the individual buildings). Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

- a) art festival
- b) food festival
- c) religious
- d) historical / folkloristic
- e) musical
- f) other cultural thematic festival (Specify:.....)

Name of the festival

Dates if established

Period of the year

Use this field if you like to provide more information.....

Name of the festivals

.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q4b: Are there any recurrent/seasonal open-air specific (cultural/traditional) activities?
If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area, and the dates/periods.

- a) agenda of cultural events
- b) theater agenda
- c) recurring exhibitions
- d) crafts fair
- e) parades
- f) religious festivities
- g) other. Specify

Name of the recurrent activity

Dates if established

Period of the year

Use this field if you like provide more information.....

.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q4c: Are there any other open-air periodical activities?
If yes, please, **draw** the boundaries of area of

- a) Daily food market
- b) Periodic food market
- c) Periodic any staff/goods market
- d) Periodic traditional market
- e) Periodic antiques market
- f) Fairs
- g) Other (specify)

Indicate:

Name of the recurrent activity
 Dates if established
 Period of the year
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
 Use this field if you like provide more information

Q4d: Please indicate if in your area there was/has been planned any extraordinary event and if possible draw/point the interest area in the map (e.g. stage of races, expo, etc.)

Indicate:

Name of the extraordinary event
 Occurred
 Planned and scheduled
 Conceived to be planned
 Dates/year
 Period of the year
 Use this field if you like provide more information

5. HISTORIC BUILDINGS AND MONUMENTS

Q5a: Are there any UNESCO World Heritage buildings in your area?
 If yes, please **point** the individual buildings.

Name
 Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
 Historical changes of use (e.g. originally church, now museum)
 Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc. archives and literary sources, bibliography).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q5b: Are there any other listed (national, local) buildings/monuments?

If yes, please **point** individual buildings/monuments. Indicate

Name

Date or period of the building/monuments

Description

Inscription year

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

...

Q5c: Are there any other historic buildings that could be relevant for local history and traditions?

If yes, please, **point** the individual buildings. Indicate

Name

Date or period of the building/monuments

Description

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

Q5d: Are there any relevant rehabilitated historic buildings that have been devoted to new relevant public/collective activities?

If yes, please, **point** the buildings.

- a) for cultural activities (please distinguish between historical building as museum and cultural activities e.g. performances, public conferences etc.)
- b) for activities related to art and festivals
- c) for migrants hospitality
- d) for public authority
- e) for tourism
- f) there aren't rehabilitated historic buildings for public uses
- g) other

Name
Date of the building/monuments
Description
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models, etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information

Q5e: Are there any relevant old/historic farms? If yes, please, point on the map.

Name
Original period (e.g. 15th Century)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q5f: Are there any relevant recent building that have been built? If yes, please, point on the map and indicate:

- a) cultural activities
- b) production
- c) sustainable energy production
- d) trade hub
- e) other. Specify

Name
Function
Year of construction
 10 to 5 years
 5 to 1 years
 less than 1 year

Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q5.g Are there any other relevant sites /buildings in your SIA?

Please point/draw in the map and indicate

Name

Function

Use this field if you like provide more information

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)
Use this field if you like provide more information
.....

Q5.h According to the cultural heritage buildings that you have pointed and listed, please provide more specific documentation available. In particular, provide or indicate where it is available:

Name the building

Date of construction

- a) architectural drawing
 - a. author
 - b. date
- b) 3D model
 - a. author
 - b. date
- c) photograph
 - a. author
 - b. date
- d) video
 - a. author
 - b. date
- e) other

6. The relation of your area to the closest urban area

Question 6a: Please indicate the closest and the most related urban area and **draw/point** in the map.

- a) No relevant relation, our area is self-sufficient.
- b) Limited relation, only for bureaucratic processes and governance actions.
- c) Intermediate relation, residences go to urban areas for major needs such as hospitals, municipal registrations, etc.

- d) Strong relation, majority of residences go to urban areas on a daily basis.

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Question 6b: Please indicate and **point** in the map the cultural organisations and buildings within the SIA area and/or the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) Preservation cultural heritage institutions
- b) Museums
- c) Ecomuseums
- d) Theaters
- e) Libraries
- f) Art galleries
- g) Public Archives
- h) Cinemas
- i) Archaeological sites
- j) Natural parks and protected areas
- k) Other. Specify

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6c: Please indicate and **point** in the map important education buildings within the SIA area and/or indicate the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) primary schools
- b) high schools
- c) universities
- d) special training programs (specify)

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6d: Please indicate and **point** in the map, relevant buildings of local authority and public services within the SIA area or indicate the closest urban areas where they are available.

- a) local authority
- b) regional authority

- c) hospital
- d) health clinic
- e) emergency room
- f) general market
- g) specialised market

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6e: Indicate **draw or point** in the map the access to your area and the relation of your area to the closest urban area and beyond through the most relevant infrastructures.

Use different layers or colors to differentiate the major from the minor infrastructure.

- a) highways (please draw a line)
- b) national streets (please draw a line)
- c) regional street ((please draw a line)
- d) local street relevant for the access to the SIA (please draw a line)
- e) bridges
- f) airports
- g) railway (please draw a line)
 - a. Specify major direct connections
- h) railway stations
 - a. high speed train stops
- i) bus stations (long-distance)

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6f: Are there more planned/ongoing infrastructures that can be important in linking the area within the region and/or beyond? Please indicate and **draw** in the map:

- a) airport
- b) railway
- c) street
- d) bridge
- e) travel hub

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6g: Are/were there any historical infrastructures crucial in linking the area within the region and/or beyond? Please show on the map.

- a) street
- b) bridge
- c) railway
- d) river
- e) canal
- f) paleochannel
- g) other. Specify

Please upload any relevant historical and recent visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Q6h: Please indicate if in the closest urban area there has/has been planned any extraordinary event and if possible point the interest area in the map

Indicate:

Name of the extraordinary event

Planned and scheduled

Conceived to be planned

Dates/year

Period of the year

Use this field if you like provide more information

7.Tourism

Question 7a: Please **draw/point** in the map, important tourist information offices within your area.

Please upload visual material (photograph, video, drawings, map, 3D models etc.).

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Question 7b: Please indicate if there are descriptions panels for sites/buildings of cultural interest that you've listed. Please when possible **point** in the map or specify.

Indicate if there are links to digital resources like QR code

Use this field for providing information

Please upload visual material for cultural signs (photograph, video, drawings, map, etc.)

Question 7c: Please indicate if there have been/are any old or ongoing tourist communication campaign and **draw/point** in the map if has interested specific sites/building

Name of the site/building

Year of the tourist campaign

Use this field for providing information

Please upload visual material for relevant advertising (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.)

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

8.Multimedia and Digital Tools

For the following data, please draw or point in the map if the information is coherent. If not possible, fill in the answers without point and attached the materials you can provide.

Q8a: Are there any kind of mapping and digital products/resources/tools related with your SIA?

- a) GIS
- b) 3D model
- c) Mobile APPs
- d) Video
- e) Virtual Tours desktop
- f) Virtual Tours mobile)
- g) other. Specify

Please provide the link and/or information about the creator

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Link

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Upload any visual materials

Q8b: Are there any kind of movies or advertising that have used the SIA as scenario? Have been produced some specific videos for your areas?

- a) Cinema
- b) television and information channels
- c) tourism
- d) advertising
- e) historic reconstruction in museum
- f) special events
- g) other. Specify

Please provide information

Description (Title, creator, date)

Media

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Please provide visual material

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Media

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Question 8c: Have any audio materials been produced? Could you provide information and eventually materials? Have they been produced for

- a) cultural projects
- b) interviews
- c) educational projects
- d) other. Specify

9. ELEMENTS OF DISTURBANCE

Q 9.1: Please **draw or point** if there are **elements of disturbance** that constitute fragmentation or damage the landscape' perception, and select them from the list below. Please indicate the location of these elements in the map for each selection.

- a) Telecommunication Infrastructural elements
 - i. base stations for mobile phones
 - ii. radios,
 - iii. TVs,
 - iv. Other. Specify
- b) Huge transportation infrastructures
 - i. highways,
 - ii. canals,
 - iii. highway tunnels,
 - iv. other. Specify
- c) Technological infrastructures
 - i. gas pipeline,
 - ii. power plant,
 - iii. other. Specify
- d) Electrical Infrastructural elements
 - i. electric cables,
 - ii. electric poles
 - iii. other. Specify
- e) Implantations of renewable energy products
 - i. solar panels
 - ii. photovoltaics
 - iii. wind farms
 - iv. others. of
- f) Installment of elements (potentially movable) that change the perception of the landscape
 - i. large advertisements panels
 - ii. large LCD screens
 - iii. other. Specify
- g) Commercial, industrial, or agricultural settlements with their services
- h) Quarries
 - i. Active
 - ii. Underused
 - iii. dismissed
- i) Waste facilities
 - i. Active

- ii. Underused
 - iii. dismissed
- j) Attraction areas
 - i. Amusement parks
 - ii. Camping area
 - iii. Picnic area
 - iv. Other. Specify
- k) Buildings or group of buildings that affect the character of the landscape (e.g. sprawl)
- l) New buildings that contrast with the cultural natural landscape because of
 - i. typology
 - ii. color
 - iii. materials
 - iv. decontextualized
 - v. other. Specify
- m) Improper street pavement
 - i. asphalt in a natural area
 - ii. improper finishing
 - iii. other. Specify
- n) Recurrent collective events that contrast with the landscape
 - i. Carousel
 - ii. circus
- o) New collective events that contrast with the existing landscape
 - i. Party
 - ii. Other. Specify
- p) Other. Specify

Please provide the link and/or information about the creator

Description (Author, Title, Date)

Link

Use this field if you like provide more information

.....

Please upload any relevant visual material (photograph, engraving, video, drawings, map, etc.).

RURITAGE

INPUT DATA FOR 3D MODEL GENERATION

Objective: The RURITAGE project will generate a 3D model of a replicator. This 3D model will be generated based on the CityGML standard.

Required input data: For the generation of the 3D model it is necessary to collect the following information from the case

- Geographical delineation of the study area
- Geometric representation of buildings in the area (building footprints in SHP format)
- Representative characteristics of each building:
 - Use
 - Year of Construction
 - Degree of Protection (of all the building and the different elements)
 - Height

- In case the height parameter of the buildings is not available, it will be possible to obtain this information from the surface and terrain elevation maps (DSM and DTM respectively)

The following table summarizes the information required to generate the 3D model and the format in which this information must be collected.

INFORMATION REQUIRED	FORMAT
Geographical delineation of the area	SHP or IMAGE
Geometric representation of buildings in the area	SHP
Representative characteristics of each building	SHP or XLS (with reference to the buildings in the SHP)
DSM - Digital Surface Model (if required)	ASC or CSV
DTM – Digital Terrain Model (if required)	ASC or CSV

Question 2a

Cadafter Name	Date	Description	File name
---------------	------	-------------	-----------

Question 2b

Cadafter Name	Date	Description	File name
---------------	------	-------------	-----------

Question 2d

Map Name	Date	Description	Additional info	File name
----------	------	-------------	-----------------	-----------

Question 2c

Map Name	Date	Description	File name
----------	------	-------------	-----------

Question 2e

Land use	Relevance	Prevalent cultivation	Media Name	Description
----------	-----------	-----------------------	------------	-------------

Question 2f

Craft Name	Description	Media Name
------------	-------------	------------

Question 2g

Activity Name	Location	Description	Additional info
---------------	----------	-------------	-----------------

Question 5h

Name of the building	Type of media	Media name	Description	Link
----------------------	---------------	------------	-------------	------

Additional info

Question 8a

Name	Type	Link	Additional info	Media Name
------	------	------	-----------------	------------

Question 8b

Name	Type	Additional info	Link	Media Name
------	------	-----------------	------	------------

Question 8c

Name	Produce for	Additional info	Media Name
------	-------------	-----------------	------------

Question 8d

Name	Produce for	Additional info	Media Name
------	-------------	-----------------	------------

MAP Template for Question 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9

Annex II: List of attributes for QGIS

LIST OF SHAPES: (See attributes below)

1. RM_AREA [polygon] the main area of each RM and R. (Systematic Innovation Area)
2. INF_SIA [polygon]: Influence zone of each SIA
3. LAND_USE [polygon]: The functional distribution of LAND within SIA.
4. SITE [polygon]: UNESCO Site, Conservation Area, sites of historic importance, historic itinerary, popular sites,
5. CHANGE [polygon]: destructed / changed areas /
6. ROUTE [line]: porcorso
7. OPEN_AIR [polygon]:
8. HISTORIC_BLDGS: [point] monuments and historic buildings
9. BLDGS [point]: other buildings
10. INFRASTR [point]: Infrastructural elements
11. DIST: Elements of Disturbance
12. NEAR_URB [point]: closest urban area
13. N_TOWN_BLDG: [point] buildings in nearby towns related to SIA
14. TOURISM [point]: Tourism related buildings/kiosks/info points
15. EVENT [point]: events.

LIST OF ATTRIBUTES

SHAPE 1:

RM_AREA: polygon (it should exist for all the sites)

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text (RM nominator)

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

RM_R_DESCR: text (name of RM)

- Camino de Santiago
- Maria's way
- Preserving old tradition for innovating agro-food production in Apulia
- Coffee production in world heritage landscape
- Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province

- Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island
- The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad
- Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete
- Natural hazards as intangible CNH for the human resilience in South Iceland
- A CNH-led approach in Austrátt manorial landscape
- Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development
- Wild Atlantic Way
- Old traditions and modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg
- Brand for discovering local food products and traditions in Rogaland
- Working for CNH as a way for migrants' integration in Geo-N
- Festival of love – arts connecting heritage and tradition
- Social innovation and local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche Region
- Integrated Management of Madra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins

P_ACRONYM: text (acronym of RM OR R) RM or R and which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- FSMLRPH
- HCC
- D.A.R.e.
- FCM
- PIAM
- NHMLPF
- VVO
- UOC
- Katla
- NMBU
- AEICE
- WESTBIC
- ARGE
- MAGMA UG
- Geo-N
- KULTprotour, KIBLA
- CoAPP
- IZM, DEM, IZTECH

COUNTRY: text:

- ES: Spain
- RO: Romania
- IT: Italy
- CO: Colombia
- GR: Greece
- HU: Hungary
- IS: Iceland
- NO: Norway
- IR: Ireland
- AT: Austria
- DE: Germany
- SI: Slovenia
- TR: Turkey

DESC_SIA: text (classification of SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

CHAR_SIA: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.

(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiques market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

EXTRA: numeric (extraordinary events such as OLYMPICS, European Capital, EXPO, etc.)

- 0
- 1

N_EXT: text (Name of the extraordinary event)

D_EXT: date (date of the event)

Y_EXT: numeric (year of the event it is in future)

EVENT_TYPE: text

- CE: Cultural Event
- FW: Food and wine event
- NE: Natural event
- CB: creation of a brand
- DE: Development project
- EA: economic agreement
- DP: delimitation of protected area
- Other

EVE_DESCRI: free text string describing the event

EVE_G_AREA: free text string describing the area covered by the event

EVE_SCALE: text string describing the scale of the event according to the following list:

- I: International
- N: National
- L: local

EVE_DATING: free text string reporting the date of the event

EVE_MED_TI: free text reporting name of the media connected to the event

EVE_MED_DE: free text reporting the description of the media connected to the event

EVE_MED_AU: free text reporting the name of the media author if available

EVE_MED_DA: free text reporting the date of the media if available

EVE_MED_OW: free text reporting the owner of the media

EVE_MED_LI: hypertext link containing webpage url of the media

EVE_MED_CO: free text reporting the copyright of the owner

INTER_1: text (first level of Interaction with other SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- F: Food
- M: Migrants
- A: Arts and Festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

INTER_2: text (second level of Interaction with other SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- F: Food
- M: Migrants
- A: Arts and Festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

INTER_3: text (third level of Interaction with other SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- F: Food
- M: Migrants
- A: Arts and Festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

INTER_4: text (fourth level of Interaction with other SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- F: Food
- M: Migrants
- A: Arts and Festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

INTER_5: text (fifth level of Interaction with other SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- F: Food
- M: Migrants
- A: Arts and Festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

MAP_R_ID: text (id of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_DE: text (description of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_DA: date (date of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_AU: text (author of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_PL: text (place of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_TY: text (typology of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_SC: numeric (scale of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_OW: text (owner/repository of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_FO: text (format of the most recent cadastre)

MAP_R_AA: text (name of person/organization who provided the most recent cadastre to POLITO)

MAP_R_AD: text (date when POLITO received the most recent cadastre)

MAP_A_ID: text (id of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_DE: text (description of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_DA: date (date of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_AU: text (description of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_PL: text (place of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_TY: text (typology of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_SC: numeric (scale of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_OW: text (owner/repository of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_FO: text (format of the most ancient cadastre)

MAP_A_AA: text (name of person/organization who provided the most ancient cadastre to POLITO)

MAP_A_AD: text (date when POLITO received the most ancient cadastre)

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

GIS: numeric (is there a GIS database)

- 0
- 1

3D: numeric (is there a 3D model of the city)

- 0
- 1

APP: numeric (is there a mobile app for the city)

- 0
- 1

VID: numeric (is there a promotional video for the city)

- 0
- 1

VISUAL: text (what visual materials are produced using SIA as scenario – select the most effective)

- C: Cinema
- I: television and information channels
- T: tourism
- A: advertising
- H: historic reconstruction in museum
- S: special events
- O: other

AUDIO: text (what audio materials are produced– select the most effective)

- C: cultural projects
- I: interviews
- E: educational projects

- 0: other

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM2: file name of visual 2

AU_R_IM2: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM2: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM2: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN2: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM3: file name of visual 3

AU_R_IM3: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM3: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM3: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN3: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM4: file name of visual 4

AU_R_IM4: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM4: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM4: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN4: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM5: file name of visual 5

AU_R_IM5: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM5: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM5: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN5: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM6: file name of visual 6

AU_R_IM6: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM6: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM6: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN6: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM7: file name of visual 7

AU_R_IM7: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM7: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM7: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN7: text (who has the copyright)

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 2

INF_SIA [POLYGON]: Influence Zone

Attributes

Id:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

SIA: text string which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

CHAR: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month. (IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

EXTRA: numeric (extraordinary events such as OLYMPICS, European Capital, EXPO, etc.)

- 0
- 1

N_EXT: text (Name of the extraordinary event)

D_EXT: date (date of the event)

Y_EXT: numeric (year of the event it is in future)

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM2: file name of visual 2

AU_R_IM2: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM2: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM2: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN2: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM3: file name of visual 3

AU_R_IM3: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM3: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM3: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN3: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 3

LAND_USE [POLYGON]: Land Use

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

ACTIVITY: text

- A: Agriculture
- F: Farming
- C: Commercial
- R: Residential
- T: Touristic
- P: Public
- O: Other

CHAR: text

- NA: Natural area
- UA: Unpopulated area

- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)**SIT_STATUS:** Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.**(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).**

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

HIST: numeric (if the area is historic)

- 1
- 0

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page**RM_R_IM1:** file name of visual 1**AU_R_IM1:** text (author of the image)**DA_R_IM1:** text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM2: file name of visual 2

AU_R_IM2: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM2: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM2: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN2: text (who has the copyright)

RM_R_IM3: file name of visual 3

AU_R_IM3: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM3: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM3: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN3: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 4

SITE [polygon]

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

CHAR_SIA: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- RA: Rural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- AR: Archeological
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month. (IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

EXTRA: numeric (extraordinary events such as OLYMPICS, European Capital, EXPO, etc.)

- 0
- 1

N_EXT: text (Name of the extraordinary event)

D_EXT: date (date of the event)

Y_EXT: numeric (year of the event it is in future)

POPULAR: Text

- R: Recently popular
- H: Historic
- L: In literature
- M: In media (TV/cinema)
- T: Traditional storytelling

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITICO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITICO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 5

CHANGE [polygon]: destructed / changed areas

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

O_NAME: text (old name of the site)

N_NAME: text (new name of the site)

CHAR: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- RA: Rural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.

(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winder
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

CHANGE1: text**REASON1:** text (to show if there are areas changed)

- WO: World War II
- WA: Other Wars
- UP: Urban projects
- DI: Disasters
- EV: International Events (i.e. EXPO, Olympics)
- OT: Other

DATE1: text (Date of Change)**EXP1:** text (name of change, ex: Spanish Civil War)**CHANGE2: text****REASON2:** text (to show if there are areas changed)

- WO: World War II
- WA: Other Wars
- UP: Urban projects
- DI: Disasters
- EV: International Events (i.e. EXPO, Olympics)
- OT: Other

DATE2: text (Date of Change)**EXP2:** text (name of change, ex: Spanish Civil War)**CHANGE3: text****REASON3:** text (to show if there are areas changed)

- WO: World War II
- WA: Other Wars
- UP: Urban projects
- DI: Disasters
- EV: International Events (i.e. EXPO, Olympics)
- OT: Other

DATE3: text (Date of Change)**EXP3:** text (name of change, ex: Spanish Civil War)**CHANGE4:****REASON4:** text (to show if there are areas changed)

- WO: World War II
- WA: Other Wars
- UP: Urban projects
- DI: Disasters
- EV: International Events (i.e. EXPO, Olympics)
- OT: Other

DATE4: text (Date of Change)**EXP4:** text (name of change, ex: Spanish Civil War)**CHANGE5:****REASON5:** text (to show if there are areas changed)

- WO: World War II
- WA: Other Wars
- UP: Urban projects
- DI: Disasters
- EV: International Events (i.e. EXPO, Olympics)
- OT: Other

DATE5: text (Date of Change)**EXP5:** text (name of change, ex: Spanish Civil War)**RM_R_WEBSI:** hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page**RM_R_IM1:** file name of visual 1**AU_R_IM1:** text (author of the image)**DA_R_IM1:** text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 6

ROUTE [line] (to define a percorso)

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

O_NAME: text (old name of the site)

N_NAME: text (new name of the site)

START: text (initial point)

END: text (ending point)

EXP: text explain the reason of chosen percorso (ex: religious path of Camino de Santiago)

CHAR_SIA: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters
- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.

(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITICO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITICO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

TOWN_NAME: free text string containing the name of the city where the site is located

SIT_SIA_CO: text string defining the connection to a specific SIA and which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

SHAPE 7

OPEN_AIR [polygon]

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

O_NAME: text (old name of the site)

N_NAME: text (new name of the site)

NAME_ACT: text (name of activity)

DATE_S: date (start date of activity)

DATE_E: date (end date of activity)

CHAR_SIA: Characterization of SIA

- NA: Natural area
- UA: Unpopulated area
- HU: Historic urban center
- GA: Area of gentrification
- IA: Area of old industrialization
- RI: Area of recent industrialization
- ND: Area under the risk of natural disasters

- O: Other

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month. (IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

ACTIVITY:

- AR: Art festival
- FO: Food festival
- RE: Religious
- SP: Sport
- CU: Cultural events
- TH: theater agenda
- EX: exhibitions
- CR: crafts fair
- PA: parades
- O: Other

TOWN_NAME: free text string containing the name of the city where the site is located

SITE_NAME: free text string provided by RM or R

SITE_TYPE: text string which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- Gorge
- Lake
- Falls
- Park
- Mining site
- Settlement
- Village
- Archaeological site
- Rural production
- Craft production
- Food production
- Vineyard
- Other production
- Risk area
- Altar
- Crossing
- Statue
- Beauty spot
- Asset
- Monument
- Remains
- Other

EXTRA: numeric (extraordinary events such as OLYMPICS, European Capital, EXPO, etc.)

- 0
- 1 (if 1; is it possible to have other fields visible)

N_EXT: text (Name of the extraordinary event)

D_EXT: date (date of the event)

Y_EXT: numeric (year of the event it is in future)

HIST: numeric (is it a historic open air or not)

- 0
- 1

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 8

HISTORIC_BLDG [point]: monuments and buildings

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

O_NAME: text (old name of the building)

N_NAME: text (new name of the monument)

TOWN: text (name of the town)

O_FUNCTION: text (original function of the monument)

- AR: Archaeological
- CO: Complex
- GO: Governmental
- RE: Religious (Church, Monastery, Chapel, etc.)
- RS: Residential
- PU: Public (Hospital, School, Court, City Hall)
- CU: Cultural (Museum, Theatre)
- CO: Commercial
- IN: Industrial
- MI: Military (Castle)
- PA: Palace
- O:

N_FUNCTION: text (new function of the monument)

- AR: Archaeological
- MU: Museum
- RE: Religious
- GO: Governmental
- RS: Residential
- PU: Public
- CO: Commercial
- RS: Residential
- IN: Industrial
- MI: Military
- TO: Tourism
- O: Other

BUI_TYP: text string which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- City hall

- Priesthood
- Centre
- Castle
- Chapel
- Shelter
- Monastery
- Church
- Complex
- Prison
- Palace
- Museum
- Hermitage
- Tower
- House
- Barn
- Jurisdictional roll
- Washtub
- Cell
- Mill
- Observatory
- Bath
- Farm
- Other

BUI_DESCRI: free text string describing the building

REHAB: numeric (if the building has been rehabilitated)

- 0
- 1

REHAB_MOTIV: text (motivation for rehabilitation)

- CA: cultural activities
- AF: activities related to art and festivals
- MH: migrants hospitality
- PA: public authority
- TO: tourism
- PR: private uses
- OT: other

REHAB_YEAR: date (date for rehabilitation)

SIT_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan of the site. Different than the status of the building. Here, we want to know if there is a conservation project for the site of the building.

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

SIT_SIA_CO: text string defining the connection to a specific SIA and which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

DATE_PRE: numeric (Precise construction date of the building)

PERIOD: numeric (century of construction)

ARCH: text (name of architect)

PATRON: text (name of builder)

ITIN: numeric (Building is a part of an itinerary)

- 0
- 1

ITIN_NAME: text (name of the itinerary)

ITIN_HIST: numeric (if building has always been a part of itinerary or recently included)

- 0 (recently became a part of)
- 1 (historically a part of)

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

INSC_YEAR: numeric (inscription year of the monument)

INSC_AUTH: text (authority of the inscription)

BLDG_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

BLDG_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.

(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

ACTIVITY:

- AR: Art festival

- FO: Food festival
- RE: Religious
- SP: Sport
- CU: Cultural events
- TH: theater agenda
- EX: exhibitions
- CR: crafts fair
- PA: parades
- O: Other

TOWN_NAME: free text string containing the name of the city where the site is located

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITICO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITICO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 9

BLDG [point]: monuments and buildings

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

NAME: text (new name of the monument)

TOWN: text (name of the town)

N_FUNCTION: text (new function of the monument)

- MU: Museum
- RE: Religious
- GO: Governmental
- PU: Public
- CO: Commercial
- RS: Residential
- IN: Industrial
- MI: Military
- CU: Cultural
- O: Other

BUI_TYP: text string which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- City hall
- Priesthood
- Centre
- Castle
- Chapel
- Shelter
- Monastery
- Church
- Complex
- Prison
- Palace
- Museum
- Hermitage
- Tower
- House
- Barn
- Jurisdictional roll
- Washtub
- Cell
- Mill
- Observatory
- Bath
- Farm
- Other

BUI_DESCRI: free text string describing the building

DATE_PRE: numeric (Precise construction date of the building)

PERIOD: numeric (century of construction)

ARCH: text (name of architect)

PATRON: text (name of builder)

ITIN: numeric (Building is a part of an itinerary)

- 0
- 1

ITIN_NAME: text (name of the itinerary)

ITIN_HIST: numeric (if building has always been a part of itinerary or recently included)

- 0 (recently became a part of)
- 1 (historically a part of)

SIA_REL: text (relation of building the main SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival

- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month. (**IMPORTANT:** MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto
- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winter
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

ACTIVITY:

- AR: Art festival
- FO: Food festival
- RE: Religious
- SP: Sport
- CU: Cultural events
- TH: theater agenda
- EX: exhibitions
- CR: crafts fair
- PA: parades
- O: Other

TOWN_NAME: free text string containing the name of the city where the site is located

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the

following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 10

INFRASTR [polygon] (infrastructural elements)

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

O_NAME: text (old name of the building)

N_NAME: text (new name of the monument)

TOWN: text (name of the town)

INF_CATE: text (infrastructure category)

- TR: Transport
- WA: Water
- EL: Electricity
- SE: Sewage/Canalization
- EN: Energy (Wind Mill / Solar)
- OT: Other

INF_TYPE: text string which content is one of the records provided in the following list according to the category previously described:

For “transport”:

- THW: Highway
- TST: Street
- TTR: Trail
- TSW: Square
- TTH: Travel hub
- TBR: Bridge
- TRW: Railway
- TRS: Railway station

- TBS: Bus station (long-distance)
- TO: Other

For “natural”:

- NR: River
- NC: Canal
- NO: Other

For “cultural”:

- CCH: Cultural heritage institution
- CMU: Museum
- CEM: Ecomuseum
- CTH: Theatre
- CCI: Cinema
- CO: Other

For “educational”:

- EPS: Primary school
- EHS: High school
- EUN: University
- EST: Special training programs
- ELI: Library
- EAG: Art gallery
- EPA: Public archive
- EO: Other

For “public service”:

- PLA: Local authority
- PRA: Regional authority
- PHO: hospital
- PHC: health clinic
- PER: emergency room
- PGR: general market
- PSM: specialised market
- PO: other

HIST: numeric (is it a infrastructure or not)

- 0
- 1

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

INSC_YEAR: numeric (inscription year of the monument)

INSC_AUTH: text (authority of the inscription)

BLDG_INS_Y: date (date of inscription)

STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

SIT_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

SIA_REL: text (relation of building the main SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration

- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

INF_DESCRI: free text string describing the infrastructure

INF_OR_PER: free text string describing the original period of the infrastructure

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 11

DIST [point] (elements of disturbance)

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

NAME: text (name of town)

TYPE_DIST: text (type of element of disturbance)

- T: Telecommunication
 - TB: base stations for mobile phones
 - TR: radios

- TT: TVs
- TO: Other
- R: Transportation
 - RH: Highways
 - RC: Canals
 - RT: Highway tunnels
 - RO: Other
- C: Technological
 - CG: gas pipeline,
 - CP: power plant,
 - CO: other. Specify
- E: Electrical Infrastructural elements
 - EC: electric cables,
 - EP: electric poles
 - EO: other. Specify
- I: Implantations of renewable energy products
 - IS: solar panels
 - IP: photovoltaics
 - IW: wind farms
 - IO: others.
- L: Installment of elements (potentially movable) that change the perception of the landscape
 - LA: large advertisements panels
 - LL: large LCD screens
 - LO: other. Specify
- SA: Commercial, industrial, or agricultural settlements with their services
- Q: Quarries
 - QA: Active
 - QU: Underused
 - QD: Dismissed
- W: Waste facilities
 - WA: Active
 - WU: Underused
 - WD: dismissed
- A: Attraction areas
 - AA: Amusement parks
 - AC: Camping area
 - AP: Picnic area
 - AO: Other. Specify
- B: Buildings or group of buildings that affect the character of the landscape (e.g. sprawl)
- N: New buildings that contrast with the cultural natural landscape because of
 - NT: typology
 - NC: color
 - NM: materials
 - NP: decontextualized
 - NO: other. Specify
- P: Improper street pavement
 - PA: asphalt in a natural area
 - PI: improper finishing
 - PO: other. Specify
- V: Recurrent collective events that contrast with the landscape
 - VC: Carousel
 - VI: circus
- D: New collective events that contrast with the existing landscape
 - DP: Party

- DO: Other. Specify

- O: Other. Specify

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 12

NEAR_TOWN [point] (towns)

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

NAME: text (name of town)

TOWN_REL: numeric (relation with the town)

- 1: No relevant relation, our area is self-sufficient.
- 2: Limited relation, only for bureaucratic processes and governance actions.
- 3: Intermediate relation, residences go to urban areas for major needs such as hospitals, municipal registrations, etc.
- 4: Strong relation, majority of residences go to urban areas on a daily basis.

ITIN: numeric (town is a part of an itinerary)

- 0
- 1

ITIN_NAME: text (name of the itinerary)

EVENT: numeric (any extraordinary event in nearby town)

- 0
- 1

TOWN_DESCRI: free text string describing the town and its relevance for the RM or R

TOW_G_AREA: free text string defining the region or province of belonging (ie. "Province of Burgos")

TOWN_TYPE: text string defining if the town is currently part of the itinerary or hystorical element of the itinerary or both of them; the content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- CU: Current part of the itinerary
- HI: Historical part of the itinerary
- CH: Current and historical part of the itinerary

TOW_T_RANG: free text string provided by each RM or R describing the temporal range in which the town is related to the SIA

TOWN_RELATI: text string defining if the town is included in the area or related to it, according to the following strings:

- I: Included in the area of interest
- R: Related to the area of interest

NTOWN_STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1
- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITICO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITICO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 13

N_TOWN_BLDG [point] buildings in the closes towns that can be linked to rural generation

Attributes

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_Palestina
- RM4_Salento

- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

NAME: text (name of the building)

TYPE: text (type of building)

- C: Cultural organization
- E: Educational Building
- L: Local authority
- P: Public Service
- I: Infrastructural

HIST: numeric (is it a infrastructure or not)

- 0
- 1

REG_STATUS: (text) (The legal registration status of the area. If the site is registered, for example, in both UNESCO and national level, draw all of them separately. If there are related doc, pdf, etc, attach them)

- U: UNESCO
- N: National Conservation Area
- L: Local Conservation Area
- O: Other, Non-registered

INSC_YEAR: numeric (inscription year of the monument)

INSC_AUTH: text (authority of the inscription)

BLDG_INS_YE: date (date of inscription)

STATUS: Status of master plan/conservation plan/management plan

- P: Planned
- C: Continuing
- H: Historical
- R: Recent
- O: Other

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

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DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 14

TOURISM [point] (for documenting tourism-related elements)

Attributes

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_1
- RM4_2
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

NAME: text (name of the building)

TYPE: text (type of building)

- TI: Tourist Information
- IP: Information Panel
- OT: Other

QR: numeric (is there a QR code)

- 0
- 1

ADVER: numeric (is there a tourism advertisement campaign)

- 0
- 1

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

CP_R_IM1: copyright exists (can we use it? 0: no, 1: yes)

- 0
- 1

CP_R_IN1: text (who has the copyright)

NOTES: free text string providing additional information

NOTES2: free text string providing additional information

CAMPAIGN: a number identifies if the data belong to the first or second campaign as described in the following list:

- 1

- 2

DATA_IN_AU: free text string providing the company and the name of the author how has inserted the data in the database (ex: for Aleesandra Spreafico; POLITO_AS, for Mesut Dinler; POLITO_MD)

DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SHAPE 15

LRG_EVENT

Geolocation: line, point or polygon according to the characteristic of the considered element

Attributes:

ID:

RM_R_CODE: text

- RM1
- RM2
- RM3
- RM4_1
- RM4_2
- RM5
- RM6
- RM7
- RM8
- RM9
- RM10
- RM11
- RM12
- RM13
- R1
- R2
- R3
- R4
- R5
- R6

EVE_NAME: free text string containing the name of the event

EVE_TYPE: text string defining the type of the event and which content is one of the records provided in the following list:

- CE: Cultural Event
- FW: Food and wine event
- NE: Natural event
- CB: creation of a brand
- DE: Development project
- EA: economic agreement
- DP: delimitation of protected area
- Other

TEMP_MESI: text (First two Letters of start month _ First two letter of end month. Ex. FEGI – da Febbraio a Giugno; MANO – Da Marzo a Novembre) If it is only one month: write only first two letters of the month.

(IMPORTANT: MA – Marzo; MG-Maggio).

- GE: gennaio
- FE: febbraio
- MA: marzo
- AP: aprile
- MG: maggio
- GI: giugno
- LI: luglio
- AU: agosto

- SE: settembre
- OT: ottobre
- NO: novembre
- DI: dicembre

TEMP_STA: text (stagione)

- SP: Spring
- SU: Summer
- AU: Autumn
- WI: Winder
- YE: whole year

PERIODIC: text (periodical [daily/weekly/monthly] activities)

- DF: Daily food market
- PF: Periodic food market
- PG: Periodic any staff/goods market
- PT: Periodic traditional market
- PA: Periodic antiquities market
- FF: Fairs
- O: Other

EXTRA: numeric (extraordinary events such as OLYMPICS, European Capital, EXPO, etc.)

- 0
- 1

N_EXT: text (Name of the extraordinary event)

D_EXT: date (date of the event)

Y_EXT: numeric (year of the event it is in future)

EVE_DESCRI: free text string describing the event

EVE_G_AREA: free text string describing the area covered by the event

EVE_SCALE: text string describing the scale of the event according to the following list:

- International
- National
- local

EVE_DATING: free text string reporting the date of the event

EVE_MED_TI: free text reporting name of the media connected to the event

EVE_MED_DE: free text reporting the description of the media connected to the event

EVE_MED_AU: free text reporting the name of the media author if available

EVE_MED_DA: free text reporting the date of the media if available

EVE_MED_OW: free text reporting the owner of the media

EVE_MED_FO: text string describing the format of the media according to the following list:

- website
- pdf
- other

EVE_MED_LI: hypertext link containing webpage url of the media

EVE_MED_CO: free text reporting the copyright of the owner

RM_R_WEBSI: hypertext link containing the RURITAGE webpage url of each RM or R page

RM_R_IM1: file name of visual 1

AU_R_IM1: text (author of the image)

DA_R_IM1: text (creation date of the image)

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DATA_DATE: the date referring to the day when the record is reported in the database in the following format DD/MM/YYYY

SIA_REL: text (relation of building the main SIA)

- P: Pilgrimage
- S: Sustainable Food Production
- M: Migration
- A: Art and festival
- R: Resilience
- L: Landscape

Annex III: Description of 3D modelling process

Generation of the DTM and the low poly models of the buildings

According to the final outcomes of the project, the 3D model of the historical centre of Appignano del Tronto has been produced with Rhinoceros by NURBS modelling, then the polysurfaces were converted into discretized meshes, in order to implement them within ATLAS web platform, as textured models. With this approach it was possible to vary the segmentation/discretization of the model only at the end of the modelling process which maximises its versatility, because in this way it is possible to precisely control the relation between of polygon number of each model and the overall accuracy according to the general aims of the RURITAGE project. Accurate models, in fact, with a low number of polygons are especially important for web applications or real time visualizations for architecture.

The procedure adopted is organized in different steps:

1. Collection of Data sources
2. Digital modelling of terrain
3. Digital modelling of buildings at two different level of detail (LoD): low and high poly
4. Implementation of 3D models within Atlas platform

DATA SOURCES

The following documents and references have been used as data sources in order to model the buildings of the historical centre of Appignano:

5. cadastral map at 1:2000 scale
6. ortho-images (aerial-photos)
7. road sections and architectural survey of the facades (referred to Via Roma and Via G. Massimo, North-East and South-West fronts for both roads)
8. Images captured from Google street view
9. Images of case studies before and after earthquake

And the following documents and references have been used to produce the digital terrain model (DTM):

10. cadastral map at 1:10000
11. road sections (Via Roma and Via G. Massimo)
12. Images from Google Earth Pro
13. Images from Google Maps

DTM

The first step concerns the realization of the digital modelling of the terrain (DTM). Different procedures have been tested in order to compare different geometrical accuracy outputs and different working times.

The procedure consisted into the following steps:

14. Extract the model of the terrain with Sketch-up
15. Extract the model of the terrain with Cad mapper
16. Extract the model of the terrain from Google Earth Pro by using a third-party photogrammetry software
17. Verify the accuracy of the various models by comparing the DTMs with the quotes of the terrain directly measured and reported on the cadastral map

The first test concerned the use of the in-built function of Sketch-up able to export a portion of terrain in form of a textured mesh directly from Google Maps, by setting the geographical coordinates, and import it automatically into the viewport. The second test concerned the modelling of the terrain through Cadmapper (<https://cadmapper.com/>), which is a web application able to generate a 3D Digital terrain model (and if needed also the buildings) by accessing and processing the OpenStreetMap database. However, with both methods, the extracted meshes were inaccurate compared to the cadastral map measures. Thus, because a more accurate topographic survey with contours of the terrain was not available, the terrain was modelled by using Google Earth pro, which has a much more accurate map of the reliefs. However, Google Earth Pro does not allow the users to directly download the model of the terrain, thus a third-party photogrammetry application called Agisoft PhotoScan (<https://www.agisoft.com/>) was used. With Agisoft it is possible to reconstruct, with a certain tolerance, any three-dimensional model by processing a set of photographs taken from different points of view and captured with a certain amount of overlapping area. The software, through the comparison of the pictures taken from different points of view, is able to calculate the position of each sample point and to build a point cloud which is the basis to construct the textured model. Agisoft is designed to work with pictures captured from real, however it is also possible to re-model a virtual 3Dmodel by capturing the screen while moving the point of view. Thus, a set of 35 pictures, with 50% of overlapping area, was enough to model about 20 hectares of terrain around the historical centre of Appignano del Tronto. The pictures were taken by keeping the model of the reliefs activated into Google Earth Pro and by moving the camera on a plane parallel to the tangent plane of the earth model in that point. While moving the camera around the zoom was set to max to get a better resolution of the map. After that, the pictures were processed by Agisoft that generated a reference textured mesh.

Then, the textured mesh of the terrain was imported into Rhino and it was scaled from the top view by matching the cadastral plan dimension and orientation. After that the road surveys were used to verify its accuracy (Figure 1). In some limited areas the mesh did not match perfectly the surveys, thus the mesh was corrected by moving its vertices along their Z axes manually.

Figure 1: Correcting the DTM using the road sections as references

Low definition models of the buildings

This second step concerned the 3D digital modelling of the buildings of city centre of Appignano. According to the accuracy of the references/data sources and considering the aim of the activity, the level of detail (LoD) was set to low, aiming to reduce the size of the file as much as possible while preserving the global accuracy. The volumes of the buildings were modelled without doors and windows except for the church and some buildings in Via G. Massimo, which were modelled with more detail in order to render more visual geometric references in the surroundings of the area of study, which is the area around the three demolished building (Figure 2).

Figure 2: NURBS models of the buildings of the historical centre of Appignano del Tronto using the MESH of the terrain as base

The buildings were modelled by starting from their ground floor traces (extracted from the cadastral map at 1:2000) then these traces were redrawn as closed planar curves and extruded one by one, along the Z axis, measuring their heights from the surveys of the facades. The buildings that were not directly

measurable from the surveys of the facades of Via Roma and Via G. Massimo were extracted by Google street view. The heights of the non-surveyed buildings were approximated by comparing their heights with the heights of adjacent known buildings.

The roofs were modelled by observing the aerial ortho-photos. Thus, even if the roofs are not the result of a direct survey, their topology matches as much as possible the one that is visible by the orthophotos. After finished the model, it was converted into a series of low poly meshes and imported into Autodesk 3D Studio Max, here an Ambient Occlusion map (AO) has been baked. The AO map fakes the proximity shadows typical of the global illumination. This stratagem not only helps to make the model a little bit more realistic even when it is not illuminated with any source of light (Google Earth has only a diffuse illumination), but more importantly it helps understanding better the details and the spatial relation between the three-dimensional objects.

The next step was importing the textured model into Sketch-Up to georeference it, then it was exported it into .KMZ file which is composed by a .DAE file that contains the mesh and textures data and a .TXT file (renamed with .KML extension) that specifies orientation and position of the camera, orientation and coordinates of the model.

Lastly, the .KMZ files were imported into Google Earth to verify their correct positioning and scale (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Model of Appignano del Tronto imported into Google earth

3D modelling of high poly textured models of the case studies

The next step consisted into replacing the low poly models of the buildings that was damaged by the earthquake (and subsequently demolished) with more detailed high poly models. Details and textures were only added to these three buildings because they are the focus point of the project.

The modelling of the three demolished buildings was based on:

18. Surveys
19. cadastral maps at different scales (antecedent to the demolition)
20. historical pictures
21. google street view pictures

Figure 4: High poly textured building of Via G. Massimo 19.

For what concerns the texturing phase, it was impossible to capture the façade of the buildings and use the pictures directly as textures because the buildings are no longer existent, thus historical pictures were used as references and the textures were re-designed with a photo editing software by merging different picture of brick walls, dirt, moss, plaster. By that, even if locally they do not match exactly the original appearance of the wall, the overall look of the buildings is globally close enough to the original one (Figure 4). In this case this approximation is acceptable because the models are not aimed to build a strictly accurate documentation for restorations maintenance or preservation, but they are aimed to recreate the visual look of that part of the city before and after the earthquake.

After modelled the detailed version of the buildings the future projects of the squares that will be built in the same areas were also modelled. In the ATLAS platform it will be possible to switch between the two digital versions of the area while navigating and visualizing it.

All the three models of the demolished buildings will be visualized into a popup window that will download one high poly model at a time allowing also low-end hardware to handle all the fine details. From this window it will be possible to switch between the view of the new project and the precedent building.

Implementation of DTM and 3D georeferenced models into ATLAS platform

In the last sections different strategies to visualize the 3D models of the buildings into existent web-based platforms (such as Google Earth) have been tested, and the KMZ file was used because it is the format that Google Earth requires. However, the DAE or the KMZ formats are not widespread formats. In fact, only a few applications are able to process them. Sometimes it is needed a third-party plug-in to import and export those formats. Thus, because the ATLAS platform) will collect models modelled by different Universities and professionals, the OBJ format has been chosen as reference export format because it is a more widespread and standard export/import solution, and it is usually available on every 3D modelling application. However, more tests are needed before indicating definitively which format

flat and it would be impossible to perceive the three dimension (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Model uploaded into ATLAS, on the left the model has only a white texture, on the right the model has a texture with baked lights

Further developments

In light of all the test carried out so far, some points need to be studied further before releasing an official standard procedure, mostly because the ATLAS platform is being implemented in parallel with the necessities risen up by the case study of Appignano del Tronto.

One of the points that still needs to be clarified is the best way to export and import the models into ATLAS. The fact that up to now the coordinates, the materials and the models needs to be inserted manually by accessing the source code of ATLAS does not look convenient and might need an upgrade. However, it must be also discussed who will upload which model on the platform, and how many cases ATLAS will collect, because if the models will be a limited number the manual importing procedure might be fine enough.

More work still needs to be done on the three highly detailed models of the demolished buildings and relative future projects (for now two areas already have an approved project and only one has been modelled, the third area still does not have any approved project and it will be implemented as soon as the project will be available).

As the last step, a standard procedure will be defined. These guidelines will be useful to those who want to upload any model onto ATLAS to guarantee its full compatibility. The guidelines will be proposed on the basis of the experience of Appignano del Tronto and they will be discussed with the developers of the ATLAS Platform and the other working groups.

ANNEX 4

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AND

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